

MicroSplit: Semantic Unmixing of Fluorescent Microscopy Data

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Abstract

FLUORESCENCE MICROSCOPY, a key driver for progress in the life sciences, faces limitations due to the microscope’s optics, fluorophore chemistry, and photon exposure limits, necessitating trade-offs in imaging speed, resolution, and depth. Here, we introduce MicroSplit, a computational multiplexing technique based on deep learning that allows multiple cellular structures to be imaged in a single fluorescent channel and then unmix them by computational means, allowing faster imaging and reduced photon exposure. We show that MicroSplit efficiently separates up to four superimposed noisy structures into distinct denoised fluorescent image channels. Furthermore, using Variational Splitting Encoder-Decoder (VSE) networks, our approach can sample diverse predictions from a trained posterior of solutions. The diversity of these samples scales with the uncertainty in a given input, allowing us to estimate the true prediction errors by computing the variability between posterior samples. We demonstrate the robustness of MicroSplit networks, which are trained for each splitting task at hand, across various datasets and noise levels and show its utility to image more, to image faster, and to improve downstream analysis. We provide MicroSplit along with all associated training and evaluation datasets as open resources, enabling life scientists to immediately benefit from the potential of computational multiplexing and thus help accelerate the rate of their scientific discovery process.

Keywords: deep learning, fluorescence microscopy, computational multiplexing, semantic channel unmixing, variational inference

1 Introduction

Fluorescence microscopy is an essential tool for exploring structures and dynamics within cells, tissues, and organisms. Multiplexed acquisition techniques involving multiple fluorophores, each tagged to a different cellular structure, are used to acquire multichannel image data. However, overlap in fluorophore excitation spectra imposes practical limits on the number of fluorophores that can be used in a biological sample (see Figure 1a) without problems such as cross-talk or bleed-through [1]. Even if a suitable set of fluorescent labels have been chosen, the sequential nature of multiplexed acquisitions requires multiple exposures of the sample, which reduces the photon budget available for other purposes [2, 3] and also limits the maximum sampling frequency in live-cell imaging scenarios. A limited photon budget can be addressed by reducing the photon exposure per acquisition, which in turn will lead to more noisy images that will be harder to analyze [3–5].

In this work, we describe a computational multiplexing approach, MicroSplit, which addresses the limitations outlined above. We propose labeling and imaging multiple biological structures in a single fluorescent

Fig. 1 Semantic unmixing of fluorescence microscopy data with MicroSplit. (a) Multiplexed fluorescent imaging is conducted by labeling cellular components with different fluorescent markers and imaging one after another into separate image channels. (b) We propose a method that allows multiple cellular structures to be imaged simultaneously in a single image channel. The superimposed structures are then split into separate channels using an adequately trained neural network. (c) Imaging multiple structures in one go saves precious photon budget. It is well known that the total photon budget limits the capabilities of light microscopes (left). Using content-aware denoising methods, *e.g.* [3, 4], can help repurpose some photon budget by acquiring more noisy raw images (middle). Imaging multiple cellular components in a single fluorescent channel saves additional photon budget that can then, for example, be invested into imaging additional structures, image more gentle, or image faster (right). (d-f) Exemplary qualitative results of two-channel splitting (d), three channel splitting (e), and four-channel splitting (f). Each panel shows the image channel containing multiple structures to be split (input), insets of the noisy target channels ($C_i, i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$) as they are used during training (target), and insets of the split channels as predictions by MicroSplit (prediction). Note that the predictions are noticeable less noisy than the training data itself, which is a key feature of MicroSplit’s unsupervised denoising component (see also the main text and Figure 2).

channel and then employing our proposed method to split superimposed structures from within this multi-structure channel computationally into separate unmixed image channels (see Figure 1b). We recently presented the underlying methodological components that can enable such computational multiplexing in theory [6, 7] and have now created a practical method that (i) combines the benefits of both approaches into a single framework, (ii) enables the processing of volumetric image data by creating a highly optimized network architecture for it (see Figure 1 and Table 1), and (iii) we propose a procedure to assess the calibration of a trained network and the estimation of prediction errors (see Figure 2 and Section 2.3). MicroSplit is designed for easy use by microscopists and life scientists, even those who are not machine learning experts.

Using MicroSplit allows users to (i) simultaneously image more structures than previously possible by combining up to four structures in a single channel, or to (ii) image the same number of structures but in fewer channels and, hence, at reduced photon exposure (see Figure 1c). The saved photon budget can then be allocated towards other objectives such as faster temporal sampling, better signal-to-noise ratio in raw acquisitions, *e.g.* to image more gently and avoid phototoxicity, or any combination of these possibilities. Note that each semantic unmixing task requires training a dedicated MicroSplit model. While training a universal foundation model is conceptually possible, we deliberately employ narrow, task-specific models to avoid out-of-distribution issues and to ensure robust performance on the data at hand.

Our experiments show that MicroSplit is capable of separating two, three, or even four jointly imaged structures into denoised unmixed channel predictions, even if the training data are itself noisy (see Figure 1d-f). A MicroSplit model learns to unmix superimposed structures by learning from examples (*i.e.* in a supervised way). At the same time, it co-learns to denoise the data without supervision (see Figure 2a). This means that it is sufficient to use a body of noisy training data and MicroSplit will still learn to predict denoised images for each unmixed structure (images labeled “Target”¹ in Figures 1 and 2 show such noisy training data). These properties make our method straightforward to apply in practical applications, as we show in detail in Section 2.

An additional and distinctive feature of the Variational Splitting Encoder-Decoder (VSE) networks we are using is their ability to generate multiple plausible solutions for a given input image [7]. When given inputs are unambiguous and thus can be split with high certainty, the generated solutions will closely resemble each other. In contrast, as the uncertainty in inputs increases, the diversity among the sampled solutions will reflect these inherent ambiguities by becoming more different from one another. We show that the networks we trained are *calibrated*, allowing us to estimate the otherwise hard to assess true error of predictions, even in the absence of ground truth images that are notoriously hard or even impossible to come by. Technically, this is enabled by evaluating the easy-to-compute inter-sample variability (see Section 2.3). This feature is crucial because it enables users to identify the parts of their data where MicroSplit predictions may be unreliable due to ambiguities in the fed inputs. Such regions can either be disregarded or subjected to expert review, effectively addressing a persistent challenge in AI-driven bioimage analysis—the difficulty in evaluating the accuracy of predictions [1].

We show the performance of MicroSplit on 24 2D and 5 3D semantic unmixing tasks, showing that we achieve accurate results in a wide range of noise levels and superimposed structures, consistently leading to high-quality denoised single-structure predictions.

In addition to the above-mentioned use cases, we propose a way to use MicroSplit to remove unwanted structured image artifacts by unmixing them from the structures in which we are truly interested. We showcase this capability by removing spurious fluorescent puncta from a fluorescent microscopy dataset (see Figure 4 and Section 2.4.2).

2 Results

As introduced above, MicroSplit enables microscopists to image multiple structures that would typically be imaged in separate fluorescence channels and instead: (i) capture these structures in one channel, and then (ii) unmix the superimposed structures contained in that channel by computational means. The training procedure we propose requires supervision signals (target images) for each structure to be unmixed (see Figure 1b). In the following section, we outline three practical ways to obtain suitable training data and will use them in various experimental settings to demonstrate their effectiveness.

2.1 Training Modes and Required Training Data

Traditionally, data are acquired using conventional multiplexing (see Figure 1a). Hence, we propose **Training Mode I**, where previously recorded multiplexed image channels are used as targets for supervised training to achieve semantic unmixing of cellular structures (see Figure 2a). We generate mixed input images by pixel-wise summation of multiplexed image channels. These input images closely resemble what can later be acquired in a single acquisition (see Figure 1b). Although this approach yields high-quality training data, some differences in noise properties and intensity variations between structures may arise, as discussed in Section C.2. Experiments using *Training Mode I* show consistently high semantic unmixing performance, as seen in Figures 1 and 2, Table 1, and in Sections B.2 and C.2.

¹In many supervised training settings, the supervision data is referred to as “ground truth”. In this manuscript we instead refer to the supervision signals as “Target” since MicroSplit can be trained exclusively on noisy data that is therefore not *ground truth*.

(a) Two-channel unmixing tasks

Task	Dataset	Task Details	2D/3D	PSNR		MicroMS-SSIM	
				C1	C2	C1	C2
I	HT-H24	TM-I	3D	38.8	33.8	0.970	0.951
II	HT-P23A	TM-I	3D	25.1	31.4	0.747	0.932
III	HT-P23B	TM-I	3D	26.4	21.6	0.847	0.599
IV	Pavia-P24	TM-III, high, 50:50	2D	24.3	29.9	0.682	0.839
V	Pavia-P24	TM-III, high, 66:33	2D	28.2	25.6	0.780	0.696
VI	Pavia-P24	TM-III, high, 84:16	2D	25.2	24.1	0.722	0.623
VII	Pavia-P24	TM-III, mid, 50:50	2D	23.1	24.3	0.673	0.755
VIII	Pavia-P24	TM-III, mid, 66:33	2D	24.0	22.3	0.729	0.678
IX	Pavia-P24	TM-III, mid, 84:16	2D	24.3	22.4	0.735	0.659
X	Pavia-P24	TM-III, low, 50:50	2D	21.9	23.0	0.612	0.684
XI	Pavia-P24	TM-III, low, 66:33	2D	22.9	21.7	0.593	0.564
XII	Pavia-P24	TM-III, low, 84:16	2D	23.3	22.8	0.682	0.663
XIII	HT-T24	TM-III	2D	40.3	32.8	0.978	0.951
XIV	HT-LIF24	TM-III	2D	32.0	32.9	0.965	0.960
XV	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C0 vs C1	2D	41.3	42.9	0.984	0.993
XVI	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C0 vs C2	2D	38.4	41.1	0.973	0.987
XVII	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C0 vs C3	2D	58.2	41.7	0.998	0.993
XVIII	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C1 vs C2	2D	43.7	44.9	0.995	0.995
XIX	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C1 vs C3	2D	65.4	44.3	1.000	0.996
XX	Chicago-Sch23	TM-I, C2 vs C3	2D	66.6	43.6	1.000	0.996

(b) Three-channel unmixing tasks

Task	Dataset	Task Details	2D/3D	PSNR			MicroMS-SSIM		
				C1	C2	C3	C1	C2	C3
XXI	CBG-Z18	TM-I	3D	28.1	28.9	29.1	0.920	0.929	0.913
XXII	CBG-N18	TM-I	3D	38.4	42.4	35.0	0.977	0.981	0.974
XXIII	HHMI-D25 _{8bit}	TM-I	3D	22.5	31.3	24.3	0.840	0.768	0.793
XXIV	HT-LIF24	TM-III, 2ms	2D	31.0	32.2	36.3	0.940	0.973	0.944
XXV	HT-LIF24	TM-III, 3ms	2D	30.8	32.2	36.1	0.940	0.973	0.948
XXVI	HT-LIF24	TM-III, 5ms	2D	32.9	34.3	37.6	0.960	0.983	0.963
XXVII	HT-LIF24	TM-III, 20ms	2D	37.0	39.7	41.4	0.984	0.994	0.989
XXVIII	HT-LIF24	TM-III, .5s	2D	39.5	41.6	43.1	0.991	0.995	0.995

(c) Four-channel unmixing tasks

Task	Dataset	2D/3D	PSNR				MicroMS-SSIM			
			C1	C2	C3	C4	C1	C2	C3	C4
XXIX	HT-LIF24	2D	32.1	32.5	34.2	37.6	0.964	0.959	0.983	0.957
XXX	Chicago-Sch23	2D	35.6	39.4	38.8	36.2	0.956	0.986	0.980	0.942

Table 1 Quantitative performance on two-, three-, and four-channel splitting tasks. Throughout this work, we refer to specific splitting tasks by their *Task-Id* (first column). Some of the microscopy datasets we use (column two), give rise to multiple splitting tasks, *e.g.* by selecting a subset of the fluorescent channels or using different noise levels or channel mixing weights (see Section 4.1). Such *Task Details* are in abbreviated form given in the third column along with the training mode used for the task. For tasks with Task-Id XXIX and XXX, the training modes used were TM-III and TM-I, respectively. For volumetric tasks (labeled 3D in column 2D/3D), we fed a 3D image stack to MicroSplit, which in turn also predicts 3D outputs (posterior samples). We evaluate all the tasks on held-out test sets and report MicroMS-SSIM [8] and CARE-PSNR (PSNR) metrics for each unmixed channel prediction. In Table G.3 we list all standard errors for the results in the above table. Note that Task XXIII is the most difficult semantic unmixing task of visually different cellular structures we encountered so far, particularly w.r.t. the quality of predictions for the third channel. In Section 2.5 and Supplementary Section B.1.1, we elaborate on how low SNR and several other properties of the raw data are contributing to the simplicity or difficulty of semantic unmixing, and how potentially occurring problems can be mitigated.

In cases where multiplexed data for *Training Mode I* are not available, we propose *Training Mode II*. Here, we assume that images of each single structure exist, but we no longer assume that all structures have been imaged in each sample. As before, here we also generate superimposed inputs by summing images showing different fluorescent structures. However, unlike before, summed-up input images no longer originate from the same sample, and any spatial correlations that might exist between these cellular structures are lost. Since a network trained with *Training Mode II* cannot leverage these correlations, we reasoned that *Training Mode I* should be at least as performant as *Training Mode II*. In Section C.2 we test this hypothesis and show that *Training Mode II* indeed comes with a slight performance drop in cases where the channels to be unmixed offer actionable spatial correlations that MicroSplit can leverage.

A variation of this approach, *Training Mode II-b*, was used to obtain the results shown in Section 2.4.2. Instead of summing uncorrelated sets of images, we used image data of superimposed structures. If those structures mix in some areas, but are visible in isolation in others, we cropped regions of interest (ROIs) showing individual structures and summed them randomly into superimposed training inputs. This training mode is best understood in the context of the results we present in Section 2.4.2.

Finally, in *Training Mode III*, we do not create input images by summing images of individual structures but rather acquire them also at the microscope. In this mode, as in *Training Mode I*, all structures of interest must be individually labeled to allow multiplexed imaging of the required training targets. Additionally, we acquire an additional image channel by exciting all used labels at once and collecting the entirety of the emitted light, hence, directly imaging also the superimposed input directly at the microscope. Naturally, *Training Mode III* then uses this channel instead of the summation of the target channels as input to MicroSplit. The advantage of this is that the input image is also subject to realistic image noise and that the relative intensity of the different structures is realistic as well (see results for tasks with IDs IV-XIV and XXIII-XXIX).

These training modes provide flexibility in the preparation of training data for MicroSplit, ensuring robust performance under a variety of experimental conditions and noise levels. We provide an overview of training modes in Supplementary Table G.3.

2.2 MicroSplit Yields High-Quality Unmixed Structures

To explore the performance of MicroSplit in various biological samples, imaging modalities, and training modes (see Section 2.1), we collected a total of 10 data sets and defined a total of $30 + 6$ semantic unmixing tasks, as shown in Table 1 and Table C.3. A brief overview of the datasets can be found in the Online Methods (Section 4) and more details are given in Supplementary Section F.

In Figure 1d-f we show qualitative results for three of these tasks. A quantitative assessment to the available ground truth, called training *targets* throughout this manuscript, can be found in Table 1. In the same table, we list all tasks and the achieved quality of unmixed channels in terms of CARE-PSNR (PSNR) [1] and MicroMS-SSIM [8], a variation on SSIM optimized for quantitative evaluation of microscopy image data.

Throughout all tasks, we observed average PSNR and MicroMS-SSIM values of 32.53 and 0.886, respectively, which for more common tasks, such as image denoising, would typically be considered high enough to warrant downstream processing and analysis. The lowest score of all semantic unmixing experiments still shows PSNR/MicroMS-SSIM values of 21.6/0.564 (Task III-channel 2 and Task VI-channel 2, respectively), which, depending on the desired analysis to be performed, is arguably still reliable enough for downstream analysis.

However, neither PSNR nor MicroMS-SSIM are sufficient to know how trustworthy the predictions of MicroSplit are, since these metrics can only be calculated when ground truth targets are available. For this reason, MicroSplit employs a variational training paradigm of its Splitting Encoder-Decoder Neural Network, as shown in Figure 2. The network architecture we use is similar to a hierarchical variational autoencoder (HVAE) [10], sometimes also referred to as a Ladder-VAE [11]. The most prominent difference in our setup is that MicroSplit is not an autoencoder, since the predictions are not meant to be the same as the given input. Details about the precise network architectures and the training procedure of MicroSplit can be found in Section 4.3, as well as in Section A.1 and in [6, 7]. In the next section, we show how the variational nature of MicroSplit can be exploited to estimate prediction errors caused by ambiguous inputs being fed.

2.3 Error Estimation, Data Uncertainty, and Calibration

MicroSplit exploits the variational nature of its underlying architecture to enable uncertainty quantification. Since variational networks are not simple point-predictors, but instead are capable of learning an approximate posterior of possible solutions [1], MicroSplit can efficiently sample such solutions. As for VAEs [12], more likely solutions will be sampled more frequently, suggesting that the analysis of the inter-sample variability can be a good surrogate for the uncertainty in the input data and, therefore, also for the trustworthiness of semantic unmixing results.

We tested this hypothesis and show our findings in Figure 2b,c. More specifically, we show an input patch and the lateral context that was fed to MicroSplit, two posterior samples, the difference between them as a heatmap, and the (approximate) minimum mean squared error (MMSE) prediction, obtained

Fig. 2 Network Architecture, Posterior Sampling, and Calibration. (a) MicroSplit jointly learns to denoise input images (unsupervised, blue shaded area) and split superimposed structures (supervised, red shaded area). For this, we use a hierarchical network architecture, variational training (yellow shaded area), and use lateral context (LC, [6]) for better performance. Due to unsupervised denoising, using an adequate noise model [7, 9], the supervised target images can be subject to noise, and the final prediction will still be noise-free. (b) Leftmost column shows an input patch containing three labeled structures in a single channel at native resolution (bottom) and two LC input patches that add additional spatial context surrounding the primary input patch (towards the top). Since the input is noisy, not all structural details in the data are visible. To account for this noise-induced data uncertainty, the variational architecture we use is capable of sampling plausible “interpretations” from a learned posterior of possible solutions. For each of the three superimposed image structures (C1-C3) we show two such posterior samples in columns two and three, and their difference as a heat map in column four. The fifth column shows an approximation of the posterior minimum mean-squared-error (MMSE), computed by pixel-wise averaging 50 posterior samples. The last three columns show the noisy target images (as used during training), an estimate of the pixel-wise root mean square error (RMSE) and the calibration plots for the three channels, respectively. The calibration plots show that the uncertainty estimated solely from predictions (RMV) correlate with the true prediction error (RMSE), which means that this easy-to-calculate quantity (RMV) can be used as a surrogate for an otherwise difficult-to-assess prediction error of MicroSplit. (c) Ten posterior samples for C3, the channel showing the highest estimated RMSE values in (b). Note that puncta at low estimated RMSE value locations (cyan arrows) remain relatively unchanged and closely resemble the structure present in the noisy target at that location, while puncta at high estimated RMSE locations (red arrows) show significant variations between samples in (c).

by pixelwise averaging of 50 posterior samples. We also show the target patches used to train the shown 3-channel splitting task (Task XXIII). Note also here how much lower the signal-to-noise ratio is in the training data than in the predictions of a trained MicroSplit network. Finally, we show the estimated pixel-wise root mean squared error (RMSE), computed using the 50 posterior samples that we also used to generate the previously shown MMSE solution.

The overall idea might be best conveyed by looking at a concrete example. Cyan and red arrows in Figure 2b,c point at image locations that might show puncta-like structures. Note that in the 10 posterior samples shown in Figure 2c, the locations pointed at with cyan arrows remain relatively unchanged and the predictions match the structure present in the target channel. However, those locations pointed at with red arrows change their appearance considerably from one posterior sample to the next. This is, in fact, also reflected in the estimated RMSE patches shown in Figure 2b, where higher estimated RMSE values appear precisely at locations where the posterior samples show elevated variability and is hence indicating that

Fig. 3 Segmentations on Unmixed Channels are in line with Inter-Observer Variability. We define three segmentation tasks, each on one unmixed channel predicted by MicroSplit, and compare the segmentations created by three Bioimage Analysts with each other. (a) For the three tasks at hand, we show overview images (left) and insets (right) of three two-channel splitting tasks, with the superimposed raw input image in the top row, the predicted channel to be segmented in the middle row, and a single-channel control acquisitions via regular multiplexing (target, see Figure 1a) in the bottom row. (b, c) For Task 1 and Task 2, we show segmentation results obtained by three analysts (A1-A3) obtained on the MicroSplit predictions (top row), the single-channel control acquisitions (target, middle row). The rightmost column shows overlays of the results obtained by all three analysts, with consistently segmented pixels being shown in white. The bottom row first shows the overlay of the segmentation results of a single analyst on predicted (top) vs. single channel control inputs (middle), and in the last column a box plot of all pairwise DICE scores between predicted vs. target channel inputs of the entire test set (5 images of size 1600×1600 for Task 1 and size 4096×4096 for Task 2). Note that the intra-observer variability between predicted and target segmentations (first three box-plots) are in about the same range as the inter-observer variability shown in the rightmost box-plot.

the input data is ambiguous in these regions. However, whether variability in posterior samples actually manifests itself in locations where predictions of MicroSplit are prone to error and, conversely, also only in these places, is not obvious. Posterior samples could consistently predict structures in places where they are not, or consistently predict the absence of structures where, in fact, such structures should be. To show that a trained MicroSplit network does not consistently hallucinate the presence or absence of structures, we propose to check how well calibrated the network is [7, 13–15].

A calibrated neural network is one whose predicted probabilities or uncertainties accurately reflect the true likelihood of outcomes. In the context of a regression task like the one executed by MicroSplit, calibration means that the predicted error estimates of the model align with the actual distribution of errors in the data. We therefore estimated the true error by computing the pixel error between the MMSE prediction of MicroSplit and the ground truth target images we derived from the available training data, and plotted this “true error” against the RMSE errors we described above. As the calibration plots in Figure 2b show, the true error and RMSE scale roughly linearly with respect to each other, meaning that the estimated RMSE, which can be computed from posterior samples only, is a good estimator of the true error. Hence, calibrated MicroSplit networks offer a reliable and efficient way to estimate the uncertainty of the data and, therefore, also the magnitude of the error of its predictions. This property is a considerable advantage over non-variational approaches and will help future users to (i) filter images or image regions that lead to uncertain predictions, and (ii) provide evidence to themselves and others that unmixed images do not suffer from hallucinations.

2.4 Downstream Processing of Unmixed Data

Sample preparation and microscopy data acquisition are typically only the first steps in the pursuit of scientific insight. Once images have been acquired, their content must be analyzed and quantified. In this work, we cannot cover the full breadth of image data analyses that life scientists routinely perform on microscopy data [16]. However, in many analysis pipelines, image segmentation is a key step since it determines the identity, location, shape, and relative location of biological entities of interest. In the following section, we have quantified the segmentation performance on MicroSplit predictions compared to the same analysis carried out on traditionally multiplexed image data.

2.4.1 Segmentation of Unmixed Image Data is of High Quality

We show that a typical segmentation task, as it is conducted in biological research laboratories on a daily basis, leads to comparable quality results when conducted on regular multiplexed microscopy data or on unmixed images. To this end, we compared the segmentation results of three bioimage analysts who were instructed to interactively train a pixel-classifier until they reach best-possible results. We show the results in Figure 3 and Figure S7, and explain the details of this experiment below.

First, each analyst segmented the single-channel microscopy data acquired by regular multiplexed fluorescent microscopy (Target) and the two-channel semantic unmixing predictions of MicroSplit (Prediction) without being informed about the nature of the data. We then compared the consistency between the segmentations of each analyst on the two sets of data and the consistency of the segmentations between the analysts. We observed that the variability between segmentations on target and unmixed images lies within the range of the inter-observer variability between the three analysts. We qualitatively show the segmentation results on two experiments (Tasks) in Figure 3bc and plot the measured intra-observer variabilities (A1,A2,A3) and the inter-observer variability.

Hence, in all experiments we conducted, the quality of segmentations remained unchanged when using unmixed image data compared to multiplexed images. But more interestingly, imaging two structures in a single channel can free up photon budget, which then becomes available for imaging at a higher frame rate, imaging at a higher signal-to-noise ratio, or imaging more labeled structures in additional image channels.

2.4.2 Removing Unwanted Imaging Artifacts

Naturally, MicroSplit predictions are just images and any subsequent analysis can be performed with them. As a second downstream processing example, we present an innovative way to remove imaging artifacts. More specifically, we imaged the post-mitotic neuronal marker CTIP2 in sliced hPSC-derived forebrain organoids using a secondary antibody conjugated to a 555 dye. The resulting image data not only had CTIP2+ nuclear staining (wanted signal), but also puncta that accumulated because of non-specific signal (*i.e.* undesired artifacts).

Fig. 4 Removing Image Artifacts with MicroSplit. We remove unwanted puncta present in raw microscopy data using our image unmixing approach by (i) selecting a set of cropped regions of interest (ROI) in the raw data that do not contain the unwanted structures (puncta, in this case), and other set of ROIs that do only contain said puncta without the fluorescent signal of interest, followed by (ii) creating superimposed input images by mixing (summing) randomly sampled ROIs of the two collected sets. These mixed images, together with the original pairs of ROIs, are now the input and target input used to train a MicroSplit network. (a) An example of a raw input image (left), showing labeled nuclei and unwanted puncta, and the puncta-free prediction by MicroSplit. Both images show intensity histograms in cyan and red, respectively. The dashed gray plot in the predicted image corresponds to the cyan plot of the input. The y-axes are shown on a logarithmic scale to better emphasize the puncta intensities MicroSplit successfully removed. (b) For better visual comparison, we show input and prediction insets from (a) in the top two rows, respectively, and the difference images (input - prediction) in the bottom row (red, intensities removed; gray intensities unchanged; blue, intensities increased).

Ideally, we could use MicroSplit to unmix the labeled nuclei (desired image content) and the undesired puncta (*i.e.* imaging artifacts). However, for this we would need training targets that contain only nuclei and others that contain only puncta, a requirement that the experimental setup of our colleagues does not permit. In Section 2.1, we introduce *Training Mode II-b*, the manual selection of image regions that show only the artifacts (puncta) or only the desired structures (the signal, in this example, nuclei). The selected image regions are then combined, just as in any *Training Mode II* experiment, and used to train a MicroSplit network. Since crops without puncta or crops that show only puncta are of limited size with respect to full microscopy images (the smallest crops we collected were 100×100 pixels), lateral contextualization (LC; see Figure 2a) could not be used and was therefore disabled during training. In total, we have manually cropped 82 content regions and 48 puncta regions from the data. This led to a total of $53.7M$ pixels for training and took an analyst about eight hours of focused work.

After training had converged, we evaluated the model on previously held out full-size microscopy images. A representative result is shown in Figure 4a,b. The insets in Figure 4b allow a more detailed comparison

of the raw input data containing the undesired puncta, and the predictions of the trained network. In the bottom row of the figure, we plot difference heat maps between input and prediction, which show how puncta are consistently absent in the predicted image while nuclei intensities remain mostly unaltered.

2.5 Limitations of MicroSplit

In this study, we conduct an in-depth analysis of various factors that impact the performance of semantic unmixing. Since semantic unmixing is a new method in the toolbox of microscopists, its full positive impact and its most useful application areas will only reach community consensus in the next few years. Here, we share our experience as accurately and unfiltered as possible and recommend practical and actionable steps to improve the achievable performance.

After working with semantic unmixing for a few years, we found the following data and network properties to be the key factors affecting the performance of MicroSplit: (i) multi-fold brightness differences (intensity skew) of the structures to be unmixed, (ii) the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the raw data, (iii) the degree of structural (dis-)similarity between the structures to be unmixed, (iv) helpful and reliable spatial correlations between the structures to be unmixed, and (v) the size of structures to be unmixed in relation to the input patch and receptive-field size of the used network architecture. In Supplementary Section B we further discuss limitations and mitigation strategies in greater detail.

To better understand the limitations of MicroSplit, we have varied the quality of image channels in two directions: signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and relative brightness of two imaged channels (skew). More specifically, in the Pavia-P24 dataset, we have manually chosen three laser power settings per channel corresponding to a relatively high SNR, a medium SNR, and a low SNR setting. We then acquired 9 sets of training data (for all combinations of illumination laser power settings). We quantify our findings in Section B.4, where we have trained 9 MicroSplit networks, one for each set of training data mentioned above, and observed that a higher degree of skew (unequal channel intensities) makes it more difficult for MicroSplit to pick up the weaker of the two structures (see Table ST2).

We also analyzed the effect of skewness with the HT-P23A (Task II) and Chicago-Sch23 (Task XX) datasets. In all cases, predictions seem fit for downstream processing, although we observe blurriness in predictions for the weaker channel in a skewed HT-P23A derived task. More details can be found in Supplementary Section B.4, and in Figures S8 and S9.

To look closer at the effect of the overall signal-to-noise (SNR) of the used training data, we acquired the HT-LIF24 dataset, which also partitions into multiple subsets that are imaged at increasingly shorter exposure times (and hence at lower SNR). Again, we have trained a MicroSplit network for each data subset. We ensured that the underlying content across these training sets is identical, which allowed us to do a quantitative evaluation of the performance drop as the SNR of the training data decreases. Quantitative results are shown in Table 1b, in Supplementary Section B.1, and qualitative examples are given in Figure S60 and and Figure S5. Although the results clearly show the expected trend (semantic unmixing quality decreases when using lower SNR training data), even the shortest exposure time of 2ms still leads to unmixed predictions that are fit for downstream processing and further analysis (in all cases, we measured a PSNR > 30.8 and MicroMS-SSIM > 0.94, as shown in Table 1b).

We additionally conducted experiments with synthetic Gaussian and Poisson noise on two sub-datasets from the HHMI-D25 dataset and observed that increased noise reduces the precision of fine structural details. Qualitative and quantitative results are provided in Supplementary Section B.1.1. These findings are consistent with previous observations made for denoiSplit [7]. Relative to high-SNR ground truth, MicroSplit tends to smooth fine structural details. Although other architectures may produce outputs that appear visually sharper, MicroSplit behaves in line with the well-understood behavior of models receiving ambiguous inputs: when the input does not contain enough information to uniquely determine the underlying structure, a model can either generate smooth, “averaged” predictions that minimize expected error, or produce artificially sharp predictions that commit to one of several plausible interpretations. This trade-off is known as the perception–distortion tradeoff [17, 18], which states that beyond a certain point, improving perceptual sharpness necessarily increases reconstruction error, and vice versa.

When working with noisy input images, predictions on full-sized micrographs, which are not fitting into GPU memory in one go, are prone to show some tiling artifacts [6, 7]. Since MicroSplit uses a variational network architecture and the data uncertainty in noisy inputs is higher, posterior samples (and even MMSE predictions) of neighboring tiles can have small intensity mismatches along their edges, causing said tiling artifacts. Additionally, the used network architectures are deep, having receptive field sizes well beyond the

primary input patch being fed to the network. It is therefore advisable to use *inner tiling* instead of the more commonly used *outer tiling*, as previously described in [6].

The potential downstream applications of MicroSplit include segmentation, tracking, detecting the presence or absence of certain structures, counting structures, and estimating dimensional properties such as radius or length of structures of interest. However, we would not recommend using MicroSplit’s prediction in downstream tasks that rely on precise pixel intensities.

Finally, since MicroSplit relies on distinguishable structural appearances (structural priors) for effective semantic unmixing, we performed a series of experiments to determine the sensitivity to structure similarity using the microtubule channel from the HT-LIF24 dataset. We created a series of increasingly more challenging 2-channel splitting tasks by superimposing patches from the same microtubule channel, effectively mixing structurally identical data. To provide a single parameter that can render the semantic unmixing task increasingly simpler, we decided to scale one of the two superimposed copies, resulting in structurally similar yet controllably different appearances (unscaled and scaled by factors of 1.032, 1.063, 1.125, 1.25, 1.5, and 2). The results of these experiments, see Figures S2 and S3, show that MicroSplit can successfully unmix the structures starting at the scaling factor of 1.063 (see also Supplementary Section B.3 for more details). However, network training performance improves more slowly (*i.e.* longer training is needed) as structural similarity increases, as evidenced by the delayed inflection point and convergence behavior in Figure S3. These results underscore the importance of structural dissimilarity for effective semantic unmixing, but they also highlight the capabilities of our method handling even very similar (only slightly scaled) distributions of structures.

3 Discussion

In this work, we introduced MicroSplit, a novel method that enables the semantic separation of multiple cellular structures superimposed in a single fluorescent image. Using Variational Splitting Encoder-Decoder (VSE) networks, we show that MicroSplit achieves high-quality semantic unmixing results for up to four superimposed cellular structures, while reliably denoising the given data and additionally providing a mechanism for estimating the error in its own predictions by evaluating the localized data uncertainty in the given input. This is particularly valuable in fluorescence microscopy, where the data is typically meant to be used for scientific downstream analyses, and the soundness of unmixed channels is essential.

Arguably, the greatest utility of MicroSplit lies in its ability to dramatically reduce photon exposure while still producing unmixed image channels of quality comparable to conventional multiplexed acquisitions. In Supplementary Section C.4, we quantitatively demonstrate on a representative example that MicroSplit enables about a ten-fold overall reduction in emitted photons while still leading to comparable image quality. Such gains stem from two factors, *i.e.* (i) by filtering fewer photons during image acquisition, and (ii) via MicroSplit’s built-in denoising capability. In this way, MicroSplit effectively reduces the required photon budget, such that the additionally available photons can then be used to achieve faster imaging, higher signal-to-noise images, or the imaging of additional structures that might previously not be imaged at the same time in the same sample due to photon budget limitations. This is particularly beneficial in live-cell imaging, where minimizing phototoxicity and maximizing temporal resolution are critical for many real-world applications.

Moreover, MicroSplit’s self-supervised denoising capability allows it to produce denoised predictions even when trained exclusively on noisy data. This feature is crucial for practical applications, as it reduces the need for high-quality, low-noise training data, which can be difficult or even impossible to acquire. The ability to estimate prediction errors through inter-sample variability further enhances the utility of MicroSplit, providing users with a measure of uncertainty that can guide the user to exclude unreliable images or image regions from further downstream analysis.

MicroSplit distinguishes itself from existing computational multiplexing techniques, such as spectral unmixing [19] or PICASSO [20], by requiring only a single superimposed image as input, rather than multiple images with different spectral overlaps. This not only simplifies the imaging process, but also allows for faster data acquisition, making MicroSplit particularly useful for live-cell imaging. Furthermore, our results demonstrate that in noisy conditions, MicroSplit performs better than PICASSO, highlighting MicroSplit’s robustness and applicability to real-world microscopy data (see Section C.1 and Figure S4 for an in-depth comparison to PICASSO).

Lastly, MicroSplit can also be used to remove imaging artifacts, and we demonstrate this in Section 2.4.2. This is always possible when artifacts and structures can, at least occasionally, be seen in isolation (*i.e.* non-overlapping in localized regions of the superimposed image). This is a novel and powerful way to remove structured noises (*i.e.* image artifacts) and is a truly unique feature that other content-aware denoising methods are not capable of [1].

Although MicroSplit offers all the above-mentioned advantages, it naturally also has limitations users must be informed about. As elaborated on, in detail, in Section 2.5, the performance of the model can degrade when the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the input data becomes too low, when the relative intensities of the structures to be unmixed are highly skewed, or when the structures to be unmixed are too similar to each other.

While the experiments we presented give clear examples for how microscopists can benefit from MicroSplit, they are only scratching the surface of what we believe microscopists and life scientists will be using MicroSplit and its future derivations for. Not only will currently infeasible experimental setups become possible², existing imaging protocols can be rendered more light-efficient, faster, and cost-effective. We predict that also beyond fluorescence microscopy, image unmixing will find applications, for example, in various biomedical imaging modalities. Future work could additionally explore the integration of MicroSplit with adaptive imaging strategies, where the imaging parameters (*e.g.* exposure time or laser power) are dynamically adjusted based on the uncertainty estimates provided by the model.

To make experimentation with MicroSplit easy and to reduce the entry barrier as much as possible, we have developed a comprehensive open source library³ and user-friendly example notebooks⁴ for all experiments we conducted. To this end, we have made all training and evaluation data publicly available⁵. Hence, our work is fully transparent, enables others to reproduce our results, and reuse our methods and implementations to elevate the rate of their scientific discovery process [21, 22].

In summary, MicroSplit represents a significant advance in semantic unmixing for fluorescence microscopy, enabling the simultaneous imaging of multiple structures in a single channel and addressing key limitations in imaging speed, resolution, and photon budget. Its ability to provide high-quality denoised predictions of unmixed cellular structures, along with reliable uncertainty estimates, makes it a powerful and practical tool. We believe that MicroSplit will find widespread use in a variety of biological imaging applications, enabling applications that are today simply not possible.

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²Imaging 8 or even more cellular structures on a regular microscope set up to image up to 4 fluorescent channels is one such example.

³<https://github.com/CAREamics/careamics>

⁴<https://careamics.github.io>

⁵For the time being, please find all data at <https://github.com/CAREamics/MicroSplit-reproducibility#links-to-all-datasets-used-in-the-manuscript>.

4 Online Methods

4.1 Used Microscopy Datasets

Here, we briefly describe the ten microscopy datasets we have used in this work, eight of which have been generated de novo by the authors; two others were taken from a previous publication [3]. All datasets will be publicly available, enabling full reproducibility of all experiments and results we have presented, and allowing others to directly compare their own methodological improvements to the approach we have presented.

The datasets cover a broad spectrum of noise levels (SNR), number of imaged fluorescent channels, overall intensity and relative intensity of these channels, imaging modality (*e.g.* confocal, spinning disk confocal, structured illumination, live, fixed, and expanded samples, 2D and 3D, and so forth).

Using these datasets, we have trained MicroSplit models for a total of 36 tasks in total, covering 2, 3, and 4 channel semantic unmixing experiments (as shown throughout all figures and summarized in Tables 1 and C.3). While we give an overview below, please refer to the supplement for additional details about each dataset.

All datasets are openly available (<https://github.com/CAREamics/MicroSplit-reproducibility#links-to-all-datasets-used-in-the-manuscript>). We provide a short description below with a more detailed description in Section F.

HT-H24

The HT-H24 dataset was imaged by the Harschnitz group at Human Technopole. HT-H24 dataset contains immunofluorescent staining of SOX2 (555) and MAP2 (488) in DIV25 dorsal forebrain organoids generated from WTC-11 (UCSF001-A) induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) (UCSF001-A). This is a 3D dataset and therefore enabled the creation of 3D semantic unmixing Task I.

HT-P23A and HT-P23B

The HT-P23A and HT-P23B datasets were imaged by the Pigino group at Human Technopole. These are 2-channel 3D datasets containing labeled microtubules and mitochondria. The samples have been prepared using cryo expansion microscopy [23]. In HT-P23A, the fluorescence intensity of labeled microtubules is strongly overpowered by the mitochondrial signal. In HT-P23B, we reduced the concentration of primary and secondary antibodies pertaining to microtubules to ensure a more equal signal.

Pavia-P24

The Pavia-P24 dataset was imaged at the Synthetic Physiology Laboratory in the University of Pavia. Here, we varied two important factors that affect the semantic unmixing performance, namely the SNR (high, mid and low) and relative strength of individual structures in the superimposed input (50/50, 66/33 and 84/16). We refer to these two factors in the Task-Detail column of Table 1. For example, the Task-Detail column value ‘mid, 66/33’ means that the acquisition was done with a medium SNR and the first channel used twice the laser power compared to the second channel ($66/33 = 2$).

HT-T24

The HT-T24 dataset was imaged by the Taverna group at Human Technopole. This dataset is a 3 channel confocal microscopy imaging of fixed E37 ferret brain sections. It is a 3-channel 2D dataset. The first two channels contain the SOX2 (transcription factor used to label stem cell nuclei) and Golgi marker Grasp65, and the last channel contains the superimposed image containing the above-mentioned two structures.

HT-LIF24

This dataset was imaged at the National Facility for Light Imaging at Human Technopole. Here, we imaged with five different exposure times which we refer to in the *Task Details* column of Table 1. For instance, the *Task Details* column value ‘5ms’ signifies that the acquisition used to train the task had an exposure duration of 5 milliseconds. As a result, the different acquisitions vary in their signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). We made sure that these acquisitions show exactly the same part of the sample, that is, for a given location in the specimen, we have 5 different acquired images, each imaged with a different exposure duration and, therefore, at a different SNR.

Chicago-Sch23

This is a four-channel, super-resolution (structured illumination) microscopy dataset of live human BJ fibroblast cells acquired at the Scherer Lab at the University of Chicago [24]. The four channels show: Actin (CellMask Orange), Mitochondria (MitoTracker Green), Microtubules (Tubulin Tracker Deep Red), and Nuclei (Hoechst). We create one four-channel splitting task (Task XXX) and multiple two-channel splitting tasks (Tasks XV to XX) using this dataset.

CBG-Z18 and CBG-N18

Besides the datasets we imaged for this work, we also used the publicly available CBG-Z18 (Liver) dataset and CBG-N18 (Zebrafish) dataset, originally introduced in [3].

HT-H23

The HT-H23 dataset was imaged by the Harschnitz group at Human Technopole. It imaged the post-mitotic neuronal marker CTIP2 in sliced hPSC-derived forebrain organoids using a secondary antibody conjugated to a 555 dye. The resulting image data not only shows CTIP2+ nuclear staining, but also puncta that accumulate because of non-specific signal. In general, unspecific puncta may arise due to suboptimal sample preparation, fixation issues, and/or non-specific antibody staining.

HHMI-D25

This is a six-color confocal 3D dataset of mouse liver tissue, imaged from a total of three mice, and acquired in the Feliciano Lab on the Janelia Research Campus, Howard Hughes Medical Institute (HHMI), Ashburn, Virginia, USA. Each image includes six fluorescence channels labeling distinct subcellular structures: mitochondria, cortical actin, peroxisomes, lysosomes, lipid droplets, and nuclei. Heterozygous PhAMexcised female mice carrying the Mito-Dendra2 transgene were used to provide genetic labeling of mitochondria, while the remaining structures were visualized via immunostaining. There are three sub-datasets within HHMI-D25, namely: HHMI-D25_{8bit}, HHMI-D25_{16bit}, and HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25}. In HHMI-D25_{8bit}, all images are stored as 8-bit unsigned integers, while images of the HHMI-D25_{16bit} and HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25} subsets, they are stored as 16-bit unsigned integers. The HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25} subset is additionally downsampled and therefore four times smaller in terms of pixels, now only counting 512×512 pixels per image (while the other images are of size 2048×2048).

4.2 Evaluation Metrics

In this work, we have predominantly used the metrics CARE-PSNR [3] and MicroMS-SSIM [8], which are slight alterations of PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) and SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure), respectively [1]. We did so, since CARE-PSNR and MicroMS-SSIM are designed to better assess the quality of fluorescence microscopy images than their classical alternatives [3, 8]. Please refer to Supplementary Section E for more details.

4.3 Training Details

As shown in Figure 1a, a superimposed image patch is fed to MicroSplit as input. For a k channel semantic unmixing task (in this work, $k \in [2, 3, 4]$), MicroSplit outputs k predicted images, each containing one of the structures that are superimposed in the given input patch.

MicroSplit combines the strengths of μ Split [6] and denoiSplit [7] to enable efficient semantic unmixing in fluorescence microscopy. From μ Split, we inherit the ability to incorporate lateral image context (LC) through additional inputs, which capture additional spatial information around the primary input patch at increasingly lower resolutions (see Figure 1a and Figure S1). This allows the model to leverage the surrounding image context, typically leading to improved predictions. From denoiSplit, MicroSplit adopts unsupervised denoising capabilities and the ability to generate diverse predictions, which in turn enable robust uncertainty quantification in calibrated networks (see Figure 2).

When semantic unmixing 2D image data, we employ the Hierarchical VAE (HVAE) architecture very similar to the one described in [6, 7], while for volumetric 3D data, we implemented a suitable 3D version as described in Supplementary Section A.

The loss function for MicroSplit is a weighted combination of the losses from μ Split and denoiSplit.

$$\text{loss}_{\text{MicroSplit}} = w * \text{loss}_{\text{denoiSplit}} + (1 - w) * \text{loss}_{\mu\text{Split}}. \quad (1)$$

Unless explicitly specified, $w = 0.9$ is used in all experiments. This simple design also gives us the ability to switch to pure μ Split or denoiSplit mode by simply setting w to 0 or 1, respectively.

For 3D data, the extra spatial dimension (Z) is averaged out before computing the KL loss, maintaining performance across volumetric inputs.

Please refer to the Supplementary Section A for more details on the used model architectures and further training details, or find our open implementation on GitHub (<https://github.com/CAREamics/MicroSplit-reproducibility>).

References

- [1] Shroff, H., Testa, I., Jug, F., Manley, S.: Live-cell imaging powered by computation. *Nat. Rev. Mol. Cell Biol.* (2024)
- [2] Weigert, M., Royer, L., Jug, F., Myers, G.: Isotropic reconstruction of 3d fluorescence microscopy images using convolutional neural networks. In: Descoteaux, M., Maier-Hein, L., Franz, A., Jannin, P., Collins, D.L., Duchesne, S. (eds.) *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention - MICCAI 2017*, pp. 126–134. Springer, Cham (2017)
- [3] Weigert, M., Schmidt, U., Boothe, T., Müller, A., Dibrov, A., Jain, A., Wilhelm, B., Schmidt, D., Broaddus, C., Culley, S., Rocha-Martins, M., Segovia-Miranda, F., Norden, C., Henriques, R., Zerial, M., Solimena, M., Rink, J., Tomancak, P., Royer, L., Jug, F., Myers, E.W.: Content-aware image restoration: pushing the limits of fluorescence microscopy. *Nature Publishing Group* **15**(12), 1090–1097 (2018)
- [4] Krull, A., Buchholz, T.-O., Jug, F.: Noise2Void - learning denoising from single noisy images, pp. 2129–2137 (2019)
- [5] Prakash, M., Krull, A., Jug, F.: DivNoising: Diversity denoising with fully convolutional variational autoencoders. *ICLR 2020* (2020)
- [6] Ashesh, Krull, A., Sante, M.D., Pasqualini, F.S., Jug, F.: μ Split: image decomposition for fluorescence microscopy. (2023)
- [7] Ashesh, A., Jug, F.: denoisplit: A method for joint microscopy image splitting and unsupervised denoising. In: Leonardis, A., Ricci, E., Roth, S., Russakovsky, O., Sattler, T., Varol, G. (eds.) *Computer Vision – ECCV 2024*, pp. 222–237. Springer, Cham (2025)
- [8] Ashesh, A., Deschamps, J., Jug, F.: MicroSSIM: Improved Structural Similarity for Comparing Microscopy Data. In: *BIC Workshop, ECCV, Milan* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2408.08747>
- [9] Prakash, M., Delbracio, M., Milanfar, P., Jug, F.: Interpretable unsupervised diversity denoising and artefact removal. (2021)
- [10] Vahdat, A., Kautz, J.: NVAE: A deep hierarchical variational autoencoder. In: *Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)* (2020)
- [11] Sønderby, C.K., Raiko, T., Maaløe, L., Sønderby, S.K., Winther, O.: Ladder variational autoencoders. In: *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems. NIPS'16*, pp. 3745–3753. Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA (2016)
- [12] Kingma, D.P., Welling, M.: An introduction to variational autoencoders (2019) [arXiv:1906.02691](https://arxiv.org/abs/1906.02691) [cs.LG]
- [13] DeGroot, M.H., Fienberg, S.E.: The comparison and evaluation of forecasters. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series D (The Statistician)* **32**(1), 12–22 (1983). Accessed 2025-01-26
- [14] Niculescu-Mizil, A., Caruana, R.: Predicting good probabilities with supervised learning. In: *Proceedings of the 22nd International Conference on Machine Learning. ICML '05*, pp. 625–632. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2005). <https://doi.org/10.1145/1102351.1102430> . <https://doi.org/10.1145/1102351.1102430>
- [15] Levi, D., Gispan, L., Giladi, N., Fetaya, E.: Evaluating and calibrating uncertainty prediction in regression tasks. *Sensors* **22**(15) (2022)
- [16] Schroeder, A.B., Dobson, E.T.A., Rueden, C.T., Tomancak, P., Jug, F., Eliceiri, K.W.: The ImageJ ecosystem: Open-source software for image visualization, processing, and analysis. *Protein Sci.* **30**(1), 234–249 (2021)
- [17] Blau, Y., Michaeli, T.: The perception-distortion tradeoff. In: *2018 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, CVPR 2018, Salt Lake City, UT, USA, June 18–22, 2018*, pp. 6228–6237. Computer Vision Foundation / IEEE Computer Society, ??? (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2018.00652> . http://openaccess.thecvf.com/content_cvpr_2018/html/Blau.The_Perception-Distortion_Tradeoff_CVPR_2018_paper.html

- [18] Shroff, H., Testa, I., Jug, F., Manley, S.: Live-cell imaging powered by computation. *Nature Reviews Molecular Cell Biology* **25**(6), 443–463 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41580-024-00702-6> . Accessed 2025-11-18
- [19] Zimmermann, T.: Spectral imaging and linear unmixing in light microscopy. *Adv. Biochem. Eng. Biotechnol.* **95**, 245–265 (2005)
- [20] Seo, J., Sim, Y., Kim, J., Kim, H., Cho, I., Nam, H., Yoon, Y.-G., Chang, J.-B.: PICASSO allows ultra-multiplexed fluorescence imaging of spatially overlapping proteins without reference spectra measurements. *Nat. Commun.* **13**(1), 1–17 (2022)
- [21] Nogare, D.D., Hartley, M., Deschamps, J., Ellenberg, J., Jug, F.: Using AI in bioimage analysis to elevate the rate of scientific discovery as a community. *Nat. Methods* **20**(7), 973–975 (2023)
- [22] Deschamps, J., Dalle Nogare, D., Jug, F.: Better research software tools to elevate the rate of scientific discovery or why we need to invest in research software engineering. *Front Bioinform* **3**, 1255159 (2023)
- [23] Laporte, M.H., Klena, N., Hamel, V., Guichard, P.: Visualizing the native cellular organization by coupling cryofixation with expansion microscopy (Cryo-ExM). *Nature Methods* **19**(2), 216–222 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01356-4> . Accessed 2025-02-02
- [24] Gong, D., Cai, C., Strahilevitz, E., Chen, J., Scherer, N.F.: Easily scalable multi-color DMD-based structured illumination microscopy. *Opt. Lett.* **49**(1), 77–80 (2024)
- [25] Wang, Z., Bovik, A.C., Sheikh, H.R., Simoncelli, E.P.: Image quality assessment: from error visibility to structural similarity. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* **13**(4), 600–612 (2004) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2003.819861>
- [26] Wang, Z., Bovik, A.C.: A universal image quality index. *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* **9**(3), 81–84 (2002) <https://doi.org/10.1109/97.995823>
- [27] Wang, Z., Simoncelli, E.P., Bovik, A.C.: Multiscale structural similarity for image quality assessment. In: *The Thirty-Seventh Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers, 2003*, vol. 2, pp. 1398–14022 (2003). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACSSC.2003.1292216>
- [28] Di Sante, M., Pezzotti, M., Zimmermann, J., Enrico, A., Deschamps, J., Balmas, E., Becca, S., Reali, A., Bertero, A., Jug, F., Pasqualini, F.S.: Calipers: Cell cycle-aware live imaging for phenotyping experiments and regeneration studies. *bioRxiv* (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.12.19.629259> <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/early/2024/12/22/2024.12.19.629259.full.pdf>
- [29] Walsh, R.M., Luongo, R., Giacomelli, E., Ciceri, G., Rittenhouse, C., Verrillo, A., Galimberti, M., Bocchi, V.D., Wu, Y., Xu, N., Mosole, S., Muller, J., Vezzoli, E., Jungverdorben, J., Zhou, T., Barker, R.A., Cattaneo, E., Studer, L., Baggiolini, A.: Generation of human cerebral organoids with a structured outer subventricular zone. *Cell Reports* **43**(4), 114031 (2024) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2024.114031> . Accessed 2025-07-21

A Model Architecture and Training

In MicroSplit, we have combined the benefits of μ Split [6] and denoiSplit [7], cast those ideas in a common learning framework, enabled direct training and prediction on volumetric data, and have extensively tested and evaluated its performance on a wide range of datasets and semantic unmixing tasks. We have also made openly available all training and prediction code and all data we used. We do this to foster rapid adoption of MicroSplit by the scientific community and to allow others to improve our approach and compare our results with relative ease. In this section, we will discuss in detail the aspects of the above-mentioned works that were integrated into MicroSplit. Subsequently, we also describe our loss function and important training hyperparameters.

From μ Split, we inherit the ability to efficiently incorporate spatial context using additional inputs, called *Laterally Contextualization* (LC) inputs [6]. Here we feed, next to the primary input, for which the prediction will be made, additional LC inputs that help the network to better understand the image context from which the primary input is taken (see Figure 2a and S1). These successive LC inputs are larger and larger patches centered on the primary input patch, but downsampled to the same pixel dimensions as the primary input itself. Hence, LC inputs capture the spatial context around the primary input patch but do so at lower resolutions to ensure efficient learning and predictions in a reasonably sized overall network.

The network architectures we proposed come in flavors that trade computational complexity and GPU consumption with the best possible prediction quality. Its most GPU-efficient variant, *Lean-LC*, can train on a single GPU using less than 5GB of GPU memory. If more resources are available, it is advisable to opt for setups such as *Deep-LC*, which show better predictive performance at increased computational cost.

In Figure S1, we have briefly described the three μ Split variants. The white regions correspond to features originating from the primary input patch. As in U-Net architectures, spatial resolution halves at each successive hierarchy level through pooling operations, causing these white areas to progressively diminish in size. In μ Split (and hence also in MicroSplit), the pooled embeddings undergo zero-padding before being concatenated with feature maps from lateral contextualization (LC) inputs. These LC features are processed through dedicated ‘Input branch’ sub-networks consisting of convolutional layers with non-linear activations, dropout, and normalization components. ‘Input branch’ does not have pooling operations, and so their feature maps, at each hierarchy level, maintain spatial dimensions identical to the primary-input (represented by gray regions). This preservation enables merged embeddings from both pathways to retain the original spatial dimensions throughout the network hierarchy (gray squares). This is the core idea of LC MicroSplit has inherited from μ Split. In the caption of Figure S1 we provide more details regarding the differences in the three variants of μ Split. Please refer to [6] for more details.

From denoiSplit, we inherit the ability to jointly perform unsupervised denoising, using suitable *Noise Models*. This also enables MicroSplit to sample diverse predictions from a learned approximate posterior that captures a notion of the data uncertainty, as demonstrated by our trained networks being calibrated (see Section 2.3). While also μ Split is a variational approach that is in theory capable of generating multiple predictions from its posterior, we found that denoiSplit, arguably due to its different KL-loss formulation, produces a higher diversity that is better in line with the uncertainty in the data. In Figure S1, we present the architecture of MicroSplit, which has LC inputs and Noise models, all integrated into a single setup.

As mentioned above, we also enabled MicroSplit to operate directly on volumetric image data, a possibility that was absent in both μ Split and denoiSplit.

A.1 Loss Function used to train MicroSplit

The loss function of MicroSplit is the weighted average between the μ Split loss and denoiSplit loss, that is,

$$\text{loss}_{\text{MicroSplit}} = w * \text{loss}_{\text{denoiSplit}} + (1 - w) * \text{loss}_{\mu\text{Split}} \quad (2)$$

Unless explicitly specified, $w = 0.9$ is used in all experiments we conducted. This simple design also gives us the ability to switch to pure μ Split or denoiSplit mode by simply setting w to 0 or 1, respectively.

To incorporate LC inputs into the denoiSplit setup, we observed the need to modify the KL loss formulation used in $\text{loss}_{\text{denoiSplit}}$. In denoiSplit, pixel-wise KL divergence is computed at every hierarchy level. Let KL_i denote the pixel-wise KL divergence tensor at the i^{th} hierarchy level. KL-loss component for this hierarchy level, kl_i is defined as

$$kl_i = \alpha \cdot \sum_{j,h,w} KL_i[j, h, w]. \quad (3)$$

Fig. S1 Network architectures employed by MicroSplit. This figure provides a detailed breakdown of the components shown in Figure 2a. Specifically, it illustrates the encoder-decoder structure of our architecture, which is adapted from our prior work, μ Split [6]. Since this diagram focuses on the transformation of input data into predictions, it does not include the loss terms (such as the KL-divergence loss and the noise-model-based likelihood loss). As in [6], we improve the predictive capacity of MicroSplit by feeding not only an image patch (primary input), but also additional image context. To this end, we introduced *lateral contextualization* (LC). These LC inputs capture a larger portion of the input data but at increasingly lower pixel-resolution. This lead to three meta-architectures, Lean-LC, Regular-LC, and Deep-LC, each with increasingly higher computational and GPU memory demands but also leading to increasingly higher unmixing performance. The gray region shown in the embeddings in all three meta-architectures represents the extra spatial size in the embeddings coming solely due to LC inputs. In Lean-LC, embeddings of different hierarchy levels in the encoder benefit from LC inputs, but the decoder does not. In Regular-LC, a more GPU-consuming variation, both the encoder’s and the decoder’s embeddings use LC (*i.e.* show gray regions in the figure). Finally, since in Regular-LC the spatial dimensions of the embedding layers do not decrease, it enabled us to stack some additional hierarchy levels on top of the previously used ones. We labeled the resulting architecture as Deep-LC, the most performant but also most resource heavy variation. In order to get best results, we have used Deep-LC whenever possible, but it is important to note that with just two simple hyper-parameter switches, one can instantly make use of Regular-LC or Lean-LC and train on cheaper and older consumer GPUs.

With LC inputs, the spatial dimensions of the latent space tensors and therefore KL_i do not decrease and the summing operation in this formulation leads to a higher value, owing to the larger number of summands (which are all non-negative). This gives unnecessarily high weight to the KL loss with respect to the likelihood loss component. We observed that this degrades the performance. To handle this, we center-cropped KL_i to the shape they would assume if there were no LC inputs. Let $KL_i^{cropped}$ denote the appropriately center-cropped version of KL_i . Our modified KL loss for denoSplit becomes

$$kl_i = \alpha \cdot \sum_{j,h,w} KL_i^{cropped}[j, h, w]. \quad (4)$$

We encountered a very similar issue when working with volumetric data. In that case, pixel-wise KL-divergence is a 4-dimensional tensor $C \times Z \times H_i \times W_i$. As we work with larger and larger Z , the summation in Equation 3 would increase since the summation would be on all 4 dimensions. This again leads to giving more weight to the KL loss component against the likelihood loss, thus rendering the performance inferior. Note that this affect will become more severe when we increase the number of Z frames in the input. In other words, adding more information in the input was not beneficial. To handle this, we separately took care of the extra Z dimension by taking the average along this dimension. The resultant 3D tensor is then passed to Equation 4 to compute the KL loss component. Note that there is an additional dimension of *batch size* which we have not mentioned in the above explanation. That is because KL-loss is computed separately for every element in the batch.

A.2 Hyper-parameters used during Training

We use *PyTorch* package for creating our training and evaluation pipelines. We use a `batch_size` of 32, `max_epoch` of 400 and `learning_rate` of 0.001. We use *Adamax* optimizer and *ReduceLROnPlateau* as the learning rate scheduler with `lr_scheduler_patience` set to 150. During training, we use 16-bit precision. We use 2 LC inputs in our *Deep-LC* configuration (`multiscale_lowres_count = 3`). Please refer to our code (<https://github.com/CAREamics/MicroSplit-reproducibility>) for more details. We want to state that all experiments were done using code hosted at <https://github.com/juglab/MicroSplit>. However, we have developed <https://github.com/CAREamics/MicroSplit-reproducibility> with the objective of providing user-friendly code with easier adaptability to custom datasets.

B Analyzing Factors that Affect Predictive Performance

B.1 Pixel-noise (pixel-wise independent noise)

From our different experiments, we have found that there are two prominent factors that affect the performance on semantic unmixing tasks. The first factor is the amount of pixel-independent noise that is present in the superimposed input images and target images. More noise means inferior performance. To quantify the effect of noise, we imaged our HT-LIF24 dataset with exposure durations of *2ms*, *3ms*, *5ms*, *20ms*, and *500ms*. We imaged it such that the underlying content in these sub-datasets is identical. That is, for every frame in the *2ms* acquisition, we have the corresponding higher SNR frames in *3ms*, *5ms*, *20ms* and *500ms* acquisitions. We trained a three-channel semantic unmixing task separately for each exposure duration sub-dataset. We made predictions on the held-out test set input frames from their respective exposure duration sub-datasets. We evaluate the prediction against the target channels present in the *500ms* sub-dataset.

Although the results (Tasks XXIV-XXIX) in Table 1 show the expected trend (semantic unmixing quality decreases when using lower SNR training data), even the shortest exposure time of *2ms* still lead to unmixed predictions that are fit for downstream processing and analysis (in all cases we measured a PSNR > 30.8 and MicroMS-SSIM > 0.94). To explain the performance drop, supplementary figure S60 shows that reduced PSNR primarily results from the loss of high-frequency details.

B.1.1 Lessons learned from the difficult Task XXIII (on HHMI-D25 data)

Out of all tasks mentioned in the Table 1, the task XXIII which uses HHMI-D25_{8bit} dataset has considerable performance issues, especially in the third channel (see Supplementary Figure S57). In the next few paragraphs we will describe our approach to investigating this issue and present a working solution. We do this to provide an example for how users of MicroSplit can improve solutions that might initially not lead up to the required semantic unmixing quality.

Signal-to-noise (SNR) is one of the factors which plays a role in almost all deep-learning based methods and denoising approaches, and semantic unmixing is no exception. To investigate the role of SNR for task XXIII, we first denoised the raw data of HHMI-D25_{8bit} using Noise2Void [4], and then trained MicroSplit using those denoised images, calling this training task ‘Task XXXI’. Comparing the results of tasks XXIII and XXXI, see also Table C.3, it becomes apparent that prior denoising has a rather strong positive effect on the quality of the achieved semantic unmixing results (> 7db PSNR improvement), suggesting that the low SNR in the original data might indeed have caused the bad performance.

Since HHMI-D25_{8bit} is stored in unsigned int8, meaning that pixel values are in [0, 255], there are actually only a few distinct integer values presenting most of the data. Denoising this data, besides increasing the SNR, also increases the number of unique pixel values. We hypothesized that in addition to SNR, an overly discreet nature of pixel values might also be detrimental to semantic unmixing. To test this hypothesis, we imaged the HHMI-D25_{16bit} data subset, where the unsigned int16 format was used to store the data, increasing the pixel intensity range to [0, 65535]. Doing so, we ensured that the SNR (ratio of average foreground value to average background value) is as similar as possible for both, the 8 and 16 bit versions of the HHMI-D25 data. Using the 16bit data did indeed improve the quality of predictions, also for the problematic third channel, as can be seen in Supplementary Figures S58 and S62. The quantitative metrics in Table C.3, however, do not capture the improvement we can perceive by comparing those figures. To fully validate our hypothesis regarding SNR and overly discrete pixel intensities, we imaged another data subset of HHMI-D25, namely HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25}, which not only uses unsigned uint16 format but also bins four pixels into one (thereby increasing SNR on the cost of spatial resolution). On this data subset we defined Task XXXVI, and indeed observe a much improved semantic unmixing performance (see Table C.3 and Figure S59).

We also experimented with synthetic Gaussian and Poisson noise with HHMI-D25 dataset versions. The motivation was to start from a working setup, make the training and evaluation dataset noisy and inspect the performance degradation. For this purpose we picked HHMI-D25_{16bit} and HHMI-D25_{8bit,denoised}. We added Gaussian noise (σ) and Poisson noise (λ). Given an image x , its noisy version can be expressed $Poi(x/\lambda) \cdot \lambda + \epsilon$, where $\epsilon \sim N(0, \sigma)$ and $Poi()$ represents the Poisson distribution with parameter λ . As it was to be expected, the performance degrades with noise (see Tasks XXXII, XXXIV, and XXXV in Supplementary Figures S62, and S61, and a quantitative comparison in Supplementary Table C.3).

B.1.2 Out-of-distribution SNR

. We also use the set of models trained on different HT-LIF24 sub-datasets to understand how the performance degrades with out-of-distribution inputs. For this, we evaluate the performance of MicroSplit trained on one exposure duration on the superimposed input images coming from a different exposure duration. We present the results in Figure S5. The different curves represent individual MicroSplit models trained on one specific exposure duration sub-dataset as specified in the legend. On the x-axis, we have different evaluation sub-datasets, referred to by their exposure duration. From CARE-PSNR and MicroMS-SSIM plots, one can observe that performance improves as one increases the exposure duration. Additionally, upon observing performance on 2ms and 500ms sub-datasets, one can see that in most cases, the larger the difference between the exposure duration of the training sub-dataset and evaluation sub-dataset, the higher the performance drop. For instance, if we look at CARE-PSNR plot, the two worst-performing MicroSplit models on 2ms acquisition were trained on 20ms and 500ms. And the two worst-performing MicroSplit models on 500ms acquisition were trained on 2ms and 3ms. On a different note, one can observe much less variation in SSIM and MS-SSIM plots. We discuss this aspect in Section E.

B.2 Spatial Correlation

The structures present in the cell are spatially correlated. For example, nuclei are typically in the central regions of cells, while the cell boundary is, by definition, on the boundary of a cell. The knowledge about the cell surface, therefore, can tell something about where the nucleus should or should not be present. We wanted to understand how important this spatial correlation is for our semantic unmixing task.

For this, we worked with the Pavia-P23 dataset where we modified the input patch process during training. The default method is to pick a random location in a frame, extract patches for both structures (target channels) from that location, and sum them to create superimposed input (*i.e.* Training Mode I). Using Training Mode I, the spatial correlation between the imaged structures is naturally maintained. To disrupt this, we conducted experiments with the following alterations.

In the first alteration, we kept *Training Mode I* for 50% of all training patches, but created the other 50% of training patches by picking two different random locations and adding them together to create an input patch (*i.e.* *Training Mode II*). Hence, we maintain sound spatial correlations between the structures to be unmixed in half the training data. In the second alteration, we create all training data patches according to *Training Mode II*, thus eliminating all spatial correlations between the structures that should be unmixed and forcing the trained network to rely fully on the structural appearance of the structures only.

We report the metrics CARE-PSNR and MicroMS-SSIM in Table ST8 which shows that the absence of spatial correlation indeed results in a drop in performance by 0.3 – 0.5 dB PSNR.

B.3 Similarity of Structures to be Unmixed

Since our method relies heavily on the spatial appearance of the structures to be unmixed, we wondered how dissimilar two structures have to be to lead to good semantic unmixing results. Hence, it is best to image structures in single channels that are as dissimilar as possible.

In μ Split [6], we proposed a synthetic semantic unmixing dataset based on combinations of sinusoidal curves that required longer-range structure integration. Although the structures were very simple, the network without using LC was unable to split the input and ended up only predicting the input for both target channels equally.

However, to better evaluate to what extent a network can separate structures that have a similar appearance, we designed the following experiments. Using the microtubule channel of the HT-LIF24 dataset, we created a 2-channel splitting task by mixing patches from the microtubule channel with other patches from the exact same channel. We reasoned that the network will not be able to split structures that are literally taken from the same set of data (see bottom row in Figure S2). To give the network a chance, we then started to alter one of the two superimposed copies by scaling the data (uppermost four rows in Figure S2). This leads to the superposition of data that is structurally still very similar, but one copy will have a slightly larger appearance.

In Figures S2 and S3 we show the results of these experiments, conducted with a range of different relative scaling between the two copies of the microtubule data. The results clearly show that the network is capable of semantic unmixing the structures in all cases, even if the scaling factor was as low as 1.125. Note also that it takes the network increasingly longer before the splitting performance starts lifting off and reaching its peak, as can be inferred from the inflection point and convergence behavior seen in the PSNR *vs.* training steps plot in Figure S3.

B.4 Unequal Channel Intensities

Another factor that plays a key role in the performance of MicroSplit is the skewness in intensity between different target channels in the superimposed input image. This effect can be caused by diverging fluorophore densities for different structures, by fluorophore bleaching, or by using inadequate laser lines and/or laser power settings for some fluorophores. Any of this can lead to acquisitions where one or more of the structures are only weakly present in the superimposed input. We hypothesized that predictions for the brighter (dominant) structure should still be of good quality but that the quality for the dim structure might be worse.

To test this hypothesis, we worked with the 2-channel semantic unmixing tasks from the Pavia-P24 dataset, where we varied the laser power for the two channels we imaged from a balanced setting (50:50) to increasingly more skewed settings (*i.e.* 66:33 and 84:16). Note that the total laser power was kept the same. We acquired images at these three levels of skewness at three different total laser powers and resulting signal-to-noise ratios, giving us a total of 9 sets of image acquisitions. We show the results of all semantic unmixing experiments in Table ST2, where ‘Skew’ denotes the asymmetry in the power distribution (‘Balanced’, 50:50; ‘Mid’, 66:33; ‘High’, 84:16).

We found that, across three total laser power levels, the performance of the bright first channel generally increases as we go from Balanced to High skew. The second dim channel shows the inverse behavior. Note that since the samples we imaged at different imaging settings were not the same, each experiment is based on a different body of training and evaluation data. This causes additional fluctuations in the performance metrics we report and makes the presented results to be non-monotonic. If all 9 imaging sessions had captured the same samples, we would expect the results to show a monotonic trend.

Unequal Channel Intensities - Two Extreme Examples

For a first example, we worked with the nucleus and tubulin channels of the Chicago-Sch23 dataset. As always, we create the superimposed input by summing the two channels. Here, the nucleus is very weak (the channels being very skewed in their relative intensity), so much so that nuclei are de facto invisible to the naked eye. However, MicroSplit was still able to unmix these channels at a reasonable quality. One can observe the superimposed input, the two targets, and the predictions of MicroSplit in Figure S8.

For a second example, we inspect Task II which uses the HT-P23A dataset. Here, the two structures are microtubules and nuclei, with the latter being the weaker channel. Similarly to the first example, the weaker nucleus channel is effectively invisible in superimposed images, as can be seen in Figure S9. However, unlike in the previous example, the structure of nuclei in this dataset is less regular and more variable. Due to this and in light of the high uncertainty caused by the highly skewed channel intensities, MicroSplit MMSE predictions for the nucleus channel become rather blurry, as can be seen in Figure S9. Still, in many practical applications, *i.e.* every time the detailed texture of the nuclei is not important, such predictions can still be sufficient for the desired data analysis to be carried out.

B.5 Sufficient Lateral Image Context

Our method combines the benefits of μ Split and denoiSplit. One of the benefits of μ Split architecture we demonstrated in [6] is its ability to utilize additional surrounding spatial context for a given superimposed input patch through LC inputs and its ability to employ much deeper architectures. In [6], we showed that having sufficient spatial context helps with relatively large structures spanning hundreds of pixels.

C Additional Experiments

C.1 MicroSplit vs. PICASSO

In this section, we compare the performance of MicroSplit with PICASSO [20] (see also Figure S4). For semantic unmixing k channels MicroSplit needs as input a single superimposed image from the microscope whereas PICASSO needs k images from the microscope which correspond to k spectrally overlapping fluorophores. Due to this mismatch in the data requirement, a direct comparison is not feasible. So, to compare MicroSplit with PICASSO, we generate synthetic inputs using our HT-LIF24 dataset. However, we argue that our way of generation does not degrade the performance of PICASSO but instead, it should be easier for PICASSO to predict on this data as compared to the real data.

Since fluorophores can be ordered according to the wavelength of the maximum intensity in their emission spectra, we first define such an order of our structure types. Next, for generating every channel of the input for PICASSO, we define three weights and take the weighted average of the three structures using these weights. The weights are set according to the order of the structures set above. For example, for the first channel, the weight given to the second structure will be higher than the weight given to the third structure. We generate two sets of weights, one being harder than the other. In the hard case, the dominant structure type is given 1.5 times more weight than the next dominant type and 3 times more weight than the least dominant type. In the easy version, the dominant structure type is given 2.5 times more weight than the next dominant type and 5 times more than the least dominant type. Once the input channels are generated, we add Gaussian noise of $\sigma = 500$ to each channel independently. We also train MicroSplit on this data with the same Gaussian noise applied on top of the data. In Figure S4, we show the results on one random frame. In Table ST6 and Table ST7, we show the quantitative results.

C.2 Training Mode I vs Training Mode II- How Important are Spatial Correlations?

In this experiment, we inspect the performance drop between data acquisition types I and II. In cells, the location of different structures is often quite co-related with one another. For example, actin is mostly concentrated on the cell periphery whereas the nucleus is typically found at the center of the cell. In acquisition modes I and II, input is created by summing the crops from individual channels. In acquisition type I, since the channels are independently acquired, summing the crops of these different channels will generate an input patch where the naturally occurring co-location property cannot be preserved. In acquisition type II, since both channels are concurrently acquired, the inputs are created from summing the crops of different

Task	Dataset	Synthetic Noise	PSNR			MicroMS-SSIM		
XXIII	HHMI-D25 _{8bit}	-	22.5	31.3	24.3	0.840	0.768	0.793
XXXI	HHMI-D25 _{8bit,denoised}	-	37.9	35.2	38.6	0.990	0.903	0.974
XXXII	HHMI-D25 _{8bit,denoised}	$\sigma = 20, \lambda = 30$	31.8	27.3	32.4	0.939	0.664	0.859
XXXIII	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	-	23.2	27.9	24.8	0.772	0.849	0.779
XXXIV	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	$\sigma = 2K, \lambda = 5K$	23.2	27.9	24.8	0.827	0.861	0.778
XXXV	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	$\sigma = 4K, \lambda = 10K$	23.0	27.4	24.6	0.746	0.838	0.700
XXXVI	HHMI-D25 _{16bit,0.25}	-	32.4	32.2	35.0	0.990	0.929	0.991

Table ST1 Performance of MicroSplit on sub-datasets of HHMI-25. This table presents quantitative results of MicroSplit across various tasks defined on parts of the HHMI-25 dataset. While the original Task XXIII on HHMI-D25_{8bit} does not lead to satisfying predictions, mainly for channel 3 (see Supplementary Figure S57), tasks on similar data with higher SNR (Task XXXI, see Supplementary Figure S61, row 3), increased pixel diversity (Task XXXIII, see Supplementary Figure S62, row 2), or both (Task XXXVI, see Supplementary Figure S59) demonstrate notably improved semantic unmixing performance. Tasks XXXII, XXXIV, and XXXV are identical to Tasks XXXI and XXXIII, respectively, but with added synthetic noise, simply to demonstrate how the lower SNR drops the unmixing performance achievable with MicroSplit.

Skew	Channel 1 Laser Power			Channel 2 Laser Power		
	High	Mid	Low	High	Mid	Low
Balanced	24.3	23.1	21.9	29.9	24.3	23.0
Mid	28.2	24.0	22.9	25.6	22.3	21.7
High	25.2	24.3	23.3	24.1	22.4	22.8

Table ST2 Varying the laser power and skew with Pavia-P24 dataset. Skew column denotes the relative importance given to channel 1. High skew means larger laser power allocated to Channel 1 compared to Channel 2

channels with each crop taken from the same location in the micrographs and therefore these inputs preserve the naturally occurring co-location property. In this experiment we quantify the benefit of using this co-location information.

We work with the HT-T24 dataset which falls under *Training Mode III*. We train three models. In the first model, we create the input using *Training Mode I*, that is, we create the input by picking target patches from the same location and therefore maintain the spatial co-relation. In the second model, we use *Training Mode II*, meaning that we pick crops from random locations from the different channels and use them to create the input. This model naturally does not have access to naturally occurring spatial co-relation information in its training data. The third model is trained using *Training Mode III*. We evaluate all three models on the held-out test set where the inputs have spatial co-relation preserved and are not synthetic, that is, they are imaged from the microscope. In Table ST3, we find that the first model outperforms the second by **1.3** CARE-PSNR and **0.009** MicroMS-SSIM. Naturally, the model trained with *Training Mode III* is best and outperforms *Training Mode I* by **0.6** CARE-PSNR and **0.004** MicroMS-SSIM.

C.3 *Training Mode I vs. Training Mode III- Summed vs. Acquired Inputs*

Here, we quantify how much the performance degrades if, during training, the input is created by simply summing the two channels as compared to input coming directly from the microscope. We find that while there is indeed a performance drop as can be seen in Table ST3, the drop is not detrimental. This experiment shows the utility of our approach in the case when synthetic input is used for its training but for evaluation, inputs coming directly from the microscope are used.

C.4 MicroSplit enables a more effective use of the available photon budget

By filtering fewer photons: Traditional multiplexed imaging relies on emission filters that selectively pass photons from one fluorophore at a time in order to minimize spectral overlap. As a consequence, a substantial fraction of emitted photons is discarded, and relaxing the filters leads to bleedthrough artifacts. MicroSplit changes this trade-off because multiple structures can be imaged in the same acquisition. This allows microscopists to use substantially broader emission filters, collecting photons from several fluorophores simultaneously, without introducing the ambiguities that would otherwise arise in a multi-channel setting.

To roughly quantify this advantage, we analyzed three fluorophores from the HT-LIF24 dataset (DAPI, FITC, TRITC), using their emission spectra (downloaded from fpbase.org) normalized as probability mass

Model	PSNR	SSIM
Training Mode I: input = $C_1 + C_2$	35.9	0.956
Training Mode II: input = $C_1 + C_2$ (shuffled)	34.6	0.947
Training Mode III: input comes from microscope	36.5	0.960

Table ST3 Performance comparison for different Acquisition Modes. We use the Sox2 vs Golgi splitting task of the HT-T24 dataset for this purpose. For Acquisition Mode I and II, real input image is not used during training. Instead, input is created by synthetically summing the two target channels. In all cases, evaluation is done on the held-out test set using the real input channel, that is, on the input which is not synthetic and comes directly from the microscope.

	C1				C2			
	(2D) Z=1	Z=5	Z=9	Z=15	(2D) Z=1	Z=5	Z=9	Z=15
CARE-PSNR	35.8	38.7	39.5	39.7	30.9	33.7	34.5	34.7
MicroSSIM	0.865	0.878	0.885	0.886	0.729	0.757	0.772	0.767
MicroS3IM	0.950	0.970	0.973	0.974	0.929	0.950	0.956	0.956

Table ST4 Performance improvement with 3D models on HT-H24 dataset. As we increase the number of z-slices fed to the model, we see the performance improve in all our metrics.

	Set I			Set II		
	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_1	C_2	C_3
Input C_1	0.50	0.33	0.17	0.625	0.25	0.125
Input C_2	0.33	0.50	0.33	0.25	0.625	0.25
Input C_3	0.17	0.33	0.50	0.125	0.25	0.625

Table ST5 We use the weights to mix the three channels C_1 , C_2 and C_3 .

functions. We compared the fraction of photons transmitted by conventional multi-color filter configurations to the photons captured when using a broad, highly permissive filter suitable for MicroSplit. Across three representative scenarios, with emission filter thresholds chosen to (i) maximize photon collection, (ii) reduce bleedthrough by 25%, and (iii) reduce bleedthrough by 50%, with conventional multiplexed imaging being respectively 22%, 34%, and 55% less photons efficient than the results obtained using MicroSplit (see top half of Supplementary Figure S6).

In practical terms, this means that even in bleedthrough-optimized multiplexed imaging, each channel discards a large fraction of emitted photons, whereas MicroSplit can reclaim much of this loss by aggregating photons from multiple fluorophores in a single measurement.

By enabling gentler imaging due to denoising: Our method, next to performing semantic unmixing, also performs unsupervised denoising. Since denoising improves the signal-to-noise (SNR) of images it is applied to, microscopists can acquire the raw data more gentle, accepting a lower initial SNR [3]. To illustrate this on a concrete example, we assessed the similarity of a biological structure imaged at various exposure times between 2ms and 20ms with very high SNR data of the same regions of interest acquired at 500ms exposure time. More concretely, we have conducted these experiments on the 3 channel data (Nucleus, Microtubules, Kinetocore) of the HT-LIF24 dataset. As shown in Supplementary Figure S6 (bottom), even the denoised 2ms exposure micrographs lead to a considerably higher quality w.r.t. the 500ms images than even the 5ms raw data, for Channel 1 even compared to the 20ms raw acquisitions, suggesting at least a 3 to 10-fold reduction of the required photon budget and therefore enabling users of MicroSplit to image considerably more gentle to reach the same quality required for downstream-processing.

D Details on Uncertainty Quantification and Calibration

In this section, we detail our uncertainty estimation and calibration module. Our approach builds on the methodology of denoiSplit [7], originally inspired by [15], with a modification to the calibration process as described below. Our variational approach is inherently capable of sampling, meaning it can generate slightly different outputs for the same input each time a prediction is made. We leverage this property to produce multiple predictions for a single input, resulting in several predicted values per pixel. Using these, we calculate the standard deviation for each pixel. To ensure these pixel-wise standard deviations correspond closely to the actual prediction errors, we apply a straightforward linear scaling. Opting for

Model	Channel 1			Channel 2			Channel 3		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
PICASSO Set I	24.1	0.633	0.751	24.1	0.898	0.863	31.6	0.858	0.914
PICASSO Set II	24.2	0.638	0.757	24.1	0.904	0.864	32.2	0.841	0.911
MicroSplit	33.9	0.730	0.902	34.9	0.909	0.884	38.21	0.910	0.958

Table ST6 Quantitative comparison with PICASSO. A: RI-PSNR, B: MicroSSIM, C: MicroS3IM

Model	Channel 1			Channel 2			Channel 3		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
PICASSO Set I	.779	.021	.020	.587	.007	.012	.454	.026	.005
PICASSO Set II	.779	.032	.019	.587	.007	.012	.478	.038	.006
MicroSplit	.839	.025	.008	.475	.005	.010	.613	.012	.003

Table ST7 Standard error table for Table ST6. A: CARE-PSNR, B: MicroSSIM, C: MicroMS-SSIM

Corr.	Balanced				Mid-Skew				High-Skew			
	PSNR		MicroMS-SSIM		PSNR		MicroMS-SSIM		PSNR		MicroMS-SSIM	
0%	23.9	29.5	0.594	0.731	27.7	25.2	0.755	0.656	24.9	23.8	0.695	0.552
50%	24.1	29.6	0.614	0.761	28.1	25.5	0.761	0.657	25.1	23.9	0.781	0.699
100%	24.3	29.9	0.682	0.839	28.2	25.6	0.780	0.696	25.2	24.1	0.722	0.623

Table ST8 Here, we inspect the importance of spatial correlation in the structures. In row 1, input is created by summing patches taken from different locations. In row 2, for 50% of the time, input is created by summing patches taken from different locations. In the remaining 50% of times, input is created by summing patches taken from the same location. In row 3, all training input is created by always summing together co-located patches. Evaluation is done on co-located patches.

a linear transformation, rather than a more complex method, helps minimize the risk of overfitting. This simple linear transformation based approach allows us to easily estimate pixel-wise errors for a test input: we simply run multiple predictions, compute the standard deviation for each pixel, and then apply the learned linear transformation. Importantly, this process only requires the test input, the trained model, and the parameters of the linear transformation.

Next, we provide a technically accurate description of the methodology. For each input image x (of dimensions $H \times W$), we generate $k = 50$ predictions. At every pixel location p in channel i , this gives us k predicted values, which we use to compute the pixel-wise standard deviation $\sigma_i[p]$. Next, for calibration, for each channel i , we sort the computed pixel-wise standard deviations and bin them over $l = 30$ equally sized bins. Specifically, we implement the above-mentioned logic by storing pixel location p of the relevant pixels in these bins $\{B_i^1, B_i^2 \dots B_i^l\}$. We then compute the root mean variance (RMV) and root mean squared error (RMSE) for each channel i and bin j as

$$\text{RMV}_i(j) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|B_i^j|} \sum_{p \in B_i^j} \sigma_i[p]^2}, \text{ and} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{RMSE}_i(j) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{|B_i^j|} \sum_{p \in B_i^j} (c_i[p] - \hat{c}_i[p])^2}, \quad (6)$$

where c_i and \hat{c}_i represent the ground truth image and the estimated image for the i^{th} channel respectively. Subsequently, we fit a linear relationship between RMSE and RMV for each channel i , learning the coefficients α_i and β_i that minimize the objective

$$\arg \min_{\alpha_i, \beta_i} \|\text{RMSE}_i - (\alpha_i \cdot \text{RMV}_i + \beta_i)\|_2^2. \quad (7)$$

Note, that denoiSplit employed pixel-level regression instead of bin-based regression. However, that method has a key limitation: since images often contain many background pixels, the regression tends to be biased toward these regions, resulting in poor calibration for foreground pixels, which is problematic.

During evaluation, we sample multiple predictions for a given input. For a channel i , we compute the pixel-wise standard deviation σ_i over the multiple samples. The estimate of pixel-wise RMSE is given by

Dataset	2D/3D	Pixel size [nm]	Exposure [ms]	Pixel/Voxel (million)
Pavia-P24	2D	68	200	27.9
HT-T24	2D	110	400	2831.3
HT-LIF24	2D	285	2, 3, 5, 20, 500	4126.8
Chicago-Sch23	2D	270	100	7516.2
HT-H24	3D	285	300	1985.8
HHMI-D25 _{8bit}	3D	45	-	3850.4
CBG-Z18	3D	300	-	1362.1
CBG-N18	3D	196	-	510.7
HT-P23A	3D	37	-	637.5
HT-P23B	3D	42	-	416.5

Table ST9 Dataset Overview: This table summarizes key quantitative characteristics of the datasets used in the presented work. The column ‘Pixel/Voxel’ shows the total number of pixels/voxels in the entire dataset. Note that individual training tasks only use a (at times) small subset of the entire dataset they are derived of.

$RMSE_i = \sigma_i * \alpha_i + \beta_i$. It is worth noting that the estimation of α_i and β_i is done using the validation data and evaluation for the calibration is done on the test data.

With MicroSplit, we have presented a simple, yet effective way to estimate pixel-wise uncertainty estimates and evaluate the calibration of the predicted uncertainty. One of the advantages of the presented calibration procedure is that it does not alter the original predictions but instead learns a mapping that best predicts the measured error.

E Evaluation Metrics

SSIM (Structural Similarity Index Measure) [25, 26] and PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio) are one of the most popular metrics used in regression tasks. While MSE-based metrics like PSNR estimate pixel-wise distance between the target and the prediction, SSIM captures structural similarity. For large images that may have sub-regions having different structural characteristics, people found it useful to work with MS-SSIM (Multi-Scale SSIM) [27] instead of SSIM. Since microscopy images are typically large in pixel dimensions, MS-SSIM therefore seemed a better alternative over SSIM. However, our earlier work showed that when working with fluorescence microscopy data, especially with differing exposure durations, PSNR, SSIM, and MS-SSIM are all ill-suited [8]. Among several issues presented in the above-mentioned work, here we illustrate the issue most relevant to MicroSplit. The issue is that the input to MicroSplit is typically a noisy image which means that it was imaged using a small exposure duration. This means that the image covers a smaller portion of the full dynamic range. In other words, the pixel intensities found in the input image are relatively low in magnitude. Since the network was trained with noisy target images, which had a similar dynamic range, the prediction by the network also covers a similar amount of dynamic range. However, for the HT-LIF24 dataset, we have the corresponding high SNR target, which covers a much larger portion of the dynamic range and so has larger pixel values. So, the problem is: how to compare a prediction having a low-dynamic range with a high-dynamic range image? The core idea in the solution used in CARE-PSNR [3] and MicroMS-SSIM [8] is to estimate an optimal linear transformation for the prediction. This linear transformation makes the pixel intensity values of the scaled prediction as close to the corresponding target channel as possible. The relevant metric (PSNR, SSIM, or MS-SSIM) is then computed between the target and the scaled prediction. We have used CARE-PSNR and MicroMS-SSIM in this work.

F Dataset Details

For this work, we acquired several datasets, with some designed for specific purposes. We are making all these datasets public. Next, we briefly describe the datasets. In Table F, we provide a brief overview of the different datasets used in this work. For more details, please refer to the metadata stored in the dataset files.

F.1 The HT-P23A and HT-P23B datasets

This dataset was acquired by the Pigo group at Human Technopole, Milan, Italy. Data generation procedure was based on [23].

Cryo-ExM of MDCK-II cells

MDCK-II cells were seeded on 12 mm coverslips contained within 6-well plates at a density of 300,000 cells / well, grown at 37 degree Celsius and 5% CO₂. When cells reached approximately 50% confluence, a subset of coverslips was incubated with 150 nM MitoTracker Deep Red FM (ThermoFisher Scientific, Catalog Number M22426) for 30 minutes and checked for dye incorporation using an EVOS M5000 Imaging System (ThermoFisher Scientific). Cells were then immediately processed for cryo-ExM1. In brief, cells on coverslips were rapidly plunged frozen in -180 degree Celsius liquid ethane using a manual plunger. Coverslips were transferred to an Eppendorf tube containing frozen, desiccated acetone supplemented with .1% paraformaldehyde (PFA) and .02% glutaraldehyde (GA) for overnight freeze substitution in dry ice. The next morning, the coverslips underwent successive ethanol baths in progressively decreasing percentages, as follows: ethanol 100% (5 min), ethanol 100% (5 min), ethanol 95% (5 min), ethanol 95% (5 min), ethanol 70% (3 min), ethanol 50% (3 min) and PBS. Substituted cells then underwent anchoring in 2% acrylamide and 1.4% formaldehyde in PBS for 3 hrs. Coverslips were then exposed to activated monomer solution containing sodium acrylate (19%), acrylamide (10%), N,N'-methylenebisacrylamide (0.1%) and ddH₂O, activated by APS and TEMED (0.05%). Expansion gels polymerized for 1 hr at 37 degree Celsius, and were then denatured in denaturation solution containing SDS (200 mM), NaCl (200 mM) and Tris (50 mM) in ultrapure water at 95 degree Celsius for 1.5 hrs. Expanded gels were then washed in PBS 3X, 10 minutes for each wash. Final concentrations of solutions are reported.

Expansion immunolabeling

The following day, gels were stained with anti-alpha tubulin (ABCD Antibodies, ABCD_AA345) and anti-beta tubulin antibodies (ABCD antibodies, AA_344), diluted 1 : 300 in PBS 2% BSA. Half of the MitoTracker labeled gels were given Mouse IgG2a raised antibody, and the rest of the gels were stained with Guinea Pig IgG raised antibody. Tubulin-labeled gels were incubated at 37 degrees Celsius for 3 hrs while gently shaking. After primary labeling, gels were washed 3X in PBS 0.1% Tween, 10 minutes for each wash. Mouse IgG2a tubulin-labeled gels were then stained with Goat Anti-Mouse IgG Secondary Antibody AlexaFluor 488 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Catalog Number A-11001), while Guinea Pig IgG tubulin-labeled antibodies were stained with Goat Anti-Guinea Pig IgG Secondary Antibody AlexaFluor 647 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Catalog Number A-21450). Secondary antibody labeled gels were then incubated at 37 degrees Celsius for 3 hrs while gently shaking. The gels were washed 3X in PBS 0.1% Tween, 10 minutes for each wash. Gels were further washed 2X, 30 minutes in ddH₂O, and then placed in ddH₂O overnight for expansion.

In HT-P23A, the fluorescence intensity of labeled microtubules strongly overpowered the mitochondrial signal in the condition in which both microtubules and mitochondria were co-fluorescent in the 647 channel. To ensure a more equal signal, we imaged HT-P23B, where we reduced the concentration of tubulin Guinea Pig IgG labeling to 1:450, and the concentration of Anti-Guinea Pig IgG Secondary Antibody to 1:450 to ensure a more equal signal.

Imaging expansion gels

Expanded gels were cut into approximately 1.5 cm² pieces and placed on a 24 mm coverslip coated in poly-D-lysine (Sigma, Catalog Number P7886) and placed within a 35 mm imaging chamber. Imaging was performed on a Zeiss LSM980-NLO, in confocal mode. Z-stacks with a step size of 0.15 μ m were collected with a frame size of 2024 \times 2024 pixels using a 63X oil immersion objective (1.4NA).

F.2 The Pavia-P23 dataset

This dataset was acquired at the Synthetic Physiology Lab at the University of Pavia, Pavia, Italy.

HaCaT cell line culture and media

The HaCaT cell line was kindly gifted by Professor Hugo de Jonge (Department of Molecular Medicine, University of Pavia). Cells were maintained in DMEM/F12 no phenol red (catalog #21041-025, Gibco) with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) (catalog #10270-106, Gibco) and 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin (P/S) (catalog #A001, HiMedia). Cells were never allowed to go beyond 75–80 % confluency during routine splitting.

	Laser Power % (50/50)		Laser Power % (33/66)		Laser Power % (16/84)	
	446nm	477nm	446nm	477nm	446nm	477nm
SNR: high	40	40	27	53	13	67
SNR: mid	20	20	13	27	7	33
SNR: low	10	10	7	13	3	17

Table ST10 Laser power distribution in the several sub-datasets of Pavia-P24 dataset

Generation of the HaCaT FUCCIplex-prototype clonal cell line

The HaCaT cell line expressing the structural actin and tubulin fluorophores and the FUCCIplex sensor was generated as described previously in [28]. Briefly, cells were plated at the density of 6×10^4 cells per well in a 12-well plate and infected with the FUCCIplex lentivirus ($10\mu\text{l}$ of concentrated FUCCIplex lentivirus particles ($> 108 \text{ TU/ml}$, VectorBuilder). Positive cells were then selected with $20\mu\text{l/ml}$ of Hygromycin B (50mg/ml in PBS) (catalog #10687010, Invitrogen) and expanded. Positive cells expressing the FUCCIplex sensor were then infected with a genetically encoded Lifeact-ACTB-RFP probe (rLV Ubi-LifeAct-TagRFP, $1 \times 10^7 \text{ TU/ml}$, $10\mu\text{l}$) that specifically tags the (F-)actin filaments with a red fluorescent reporter. Lastly, the alpha-tubulin locus (TUBA1B, NM006082.3) was genome-edited via CRISPR/Cas9 using the ThermoFisher Scientific True Tag system (catalog #A42992) to tag the tubulin N-terminus of the protein with an EGFP fluorophore. Positive cells were clonally selected and expanded. The TrueTag homology arm primer forward sequence is: TCCTGTCGCCTTCGCCTCCTAATCCCTAGCCACTATGGGAGGTAAGCCCTTGCATTTCG; The reverse is: CCTGAAAGCAGCCGGGAGCCGACGGCTTACTCACACCGCTTCCACTACCTGAACC). The TrueGuide Synthetic gRNA (sgRNA) sequence is GCACGGCTTACTCACCATAG. For imaging experiments, HaCaT cells were plated in culture medium into porcine skin-coated (0.2%, w/v) ibidi μ -slide 8 well-chambered coverslips (catalog #80807, ibidi) at a density of 50.000 cells/well.

MicroSplit: Imaging Methods for Pavia-P24 dataset

Imaging was performed using a Nikon Ti2 Eclipse inverted microscope integrated with a Crest V3 X-Light spinning disk confocal unit and a Teledyne Photometrics Kinetix Scientific sCMOS camera. The dataset was acquired using a CFI SR HP Plan Apo Lambda S 100XC objective lens (silicon oil immersion, N.A. 1.35, WD 0.31–0.28mm, MRD73950).

A Lumencore Celesta Light Engine (TSX5030FV, Lumencore) provided illumination for fluorescence imaging, delivering light at multiple wavelengths (405nm, 446nm, 477nm, 520nm, 546nm, 638nm, 740nm).

Specifically, the dataset was acquired using 446nm and 477nm laser lines. In the 477nm line optical configuration, a multiband dichroic and excitation filter set (MXR00543 CELESTA-DA/FI/TR/Cy5/Cy7-A, CELESTA) was used, along with a FITC emission filter (MXR00541 FITC, CELESTA). Instead, the 446nm optical configuration was equipped with dual-band filters for dichroic, excitation, and emission (MXR00544 - CELESTA CFP/YFP, CELESTA).

In addition, the microscope has an advanced environment setup to support live imaging experiments. The Oko-Cage incubation system (Okolab) equipped with environment controllers can maintain optimal conditions for live-cell imaging, including a temperature setpoint of 37 degrees Celsius, passive humidity control, and CO_2 levels of 5%.

Nikon NIS Elements software (version 5.42.06, Nikon) was used to manage the imaging system. Spinning disk confocal mode was selected for this dataset of two-channel z-stacks. In detail, channels 477nm and 446nm were imaged sequentially with identical exposure settings (200ms). Splitting performance was tested by changing two factors: the signal-to-noise(SNR) level (high, mid, and low) and the relative laser power percentage of each channel, as shown in the table ST10.

Multiple Z-stacks of 6 planes with a step size of 1 μm were acquired to populate the dataset for each condition.

F.3 The HT-H24 dataset

The HT-H24 dataset was imaged by the Harschnitz group at Human Technopole and contains immunofluorescent staining of SOX2 (555) and MAP2 (488) in DIV25 dorsal forebrain organoids generated from WTC-11 (UCSFi001-A) induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) (UCSFi001-A). Human iPSC-derived forebrain organoids were generated following a triple-inhibition patterning protocol, without LIF supplementation, as published in a previous work [29]. At days in vitro (DIV) 25, forebrain organoids were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde at 4 degrees Celsius overnight, transferred in PBS with 30% sucrose until

fully immersed, embedded in OCT compound (Scigen), frozen rapidly, and stored at -20 degrees Celsius. 15 micrometer-thick sections were sliced on a cryostat (Leica). For immunofluorescence staining, organoid slices were rinsed in PBS, incubated with Retrieval Solution (Dako) for 45 minutes at 70 degrees Celsius, permeabilized with 0.5% Triton X-100 in PBS1x for 20 minutes, and blocked with 0.1% Triton X-100, 10% Donkey Serum in PBS1x for 1 hour at room temperature. Sections were incubated with either Rat α SOX2 1:200 (Invitrogen, 14-9811-82), and Chicken α MAP2 1:5000 (Invitrogen, PA1-10005), or Rat α CTIP2 1:500 (Abcam, ab18465) overnight, and counterstained with 1:1000 Donkey α Chicken Alexa Fluor 488 (Jackson ImmunoResearch, 703-545-155), or 1:1000 Donkey α Rat Alexa FluorTM Plus 555 (Invitrogen, A48270). Nuclei were stained with DAPI (Thermo Fisher, 62248). Immunostained sections were scanned using Ti2 CREST spinning disk (Nikon), with objective magnification of 40x.

F.4 The HT-T24 dataset

This dataset is a 3 channels confocal microscopy imaging of fixed E37 ferret brain sections acquired by the Taverna group at Human Technopole. It is a 3 channel 2D dataset. The first two channels contain the SOX2 (transcription factor used to label stem cell nuclei) and Golgi marker Grasp65, and the last channel contains the superimposed image containing the above-mentioned two structures. For more details, please look into the metadata of the dataset files. **Organism** is Ferret (*Mustela furo*) and the **Sample** is Cryosection of E37 ferret brain stained with SOX2 and GRASP65 antibodies.

Experimental Animals

All experimental procedures were conducted in agreement with the German Animal Welfare Legislation after approval by the Landesdirektion Sachsen (license for ferret TVV2/2015). Animals used for this study were kept in standardized hygienic conditions at the Biomedical Services Facility (BMS) of the MPI-CBG with free access to food and water. All experiments were performed in the dorsolateral telencephalon of ferret embryos, at a medial position along the rostro-caudal axis at a stage corresponding to mid-neurogenesis.

Protocol for immunofluorescence staining

After incubation at 70°C for 30 min in Dako Target Retrieval Solution, Citrate pH 6, cryosections were permeabilized with 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS for 30 minutes at room temperature. Blocking was performed in a blocking solution (0.2% gelatin, 300 mM NaCl, 0.3% Triton X-100 in PBS) for 30 min. Primary antibodies were incubated in the blocking solution for O/N at 4 degree Celsius. The following antibodies were used: SOX2 (goat polyclonal, AF2018, 1:200, R&D Systems) and GRASP65 (rabbit polyclonal, PA3-910, 1:200, Invitrogen). Subsequently, the sections were washed three times in PBS and incubated for 1 hour at room temperature with the following secondary antibodies: donkey anti-Goat IgG(H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 555 (A32816, 1:500, Invitrogen) and donkey anti-Rabbit IgG(H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor Plus 647 (A32795, 1:500, Invitrogen). After three washes in PBS, stained sections were mounted with Mowiol.

Acquisitions of HT-T24 dataset

All images were acquired using a spinning disk confocal system, consisting of a CrestOptics V3 light scan-head (configured with 50 μ m-pinholes) mounted on a Nikon Ti2-E inverted microscope equipped with a motorized stage and 4 Photometrics Prime 95B 25 mm cameras (pixel size 11 μ m). The samples were acquired in confocal mode with a Plan Aplanachromat Lambda S 100x/1.35 silicon immersion objective using Celesta Lumencor solid-state lasers as the light source. Fluorescence was collected using the following elements: Channel 1 (C1) - excitation wavelength 638 nm laser lines at 20%, excitation filter and dichroic mirror MXR00543-CELESTA-DAPI/FITC/TRITC/Cy5/Cy7-Full Multiband Penta, Cy5 emission filter; Channel 2 (C2) - excitation wavelength 547 nm laser lines at 20%, excitation filter and dichroic mirror MXR00543-CELESTA-DAPI/FITC/TRITC/Cy5/Cy7-Full Multiband Penta, TRITC emission filter; superimposed channel (Input) - excitation wavelength 547 nm and 638 nm laser lines both at 20%, excitation filter and dichroic mirror MXR00543-CELESTA-DAPI/FITC/TRITC/Cy5/Cy7-Full Multiband Penta, no emission filter. All images were acquired with the same camera parameters: binning 1, 16 bit and 400 ms of exposure time. For every field of view, a Z-stack with a 1 μ m-step size was acquired. Once the parameters of acquisition had been defined, they were kept constant. The software used for all acquisitions was NIS Elements AR 5.42.02 (Nikon).

F.5 The HT-LIF24 dataset

This dataset was acquired at the Light Imaging Facility at Human Technopole, Milan, Italy.

Sample preparation of HT-LIF24 dataset

HeLa cells were maintained in DMEM (EuroClone) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Thermo Fisher Scientific), supplemented with 2mM L-glutamine (EuroClone) and penicillin/streptomycin both 100 μ g/ml (EuroClone), at 37 degree Celsius in a humidified atmosphere and 5% CO₂. Cells were plated onto glass #1.5 coverslips for immunofluorescence microscopy and then fixed with 4% PFA for 10 min. They were permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 and 0.2% BSA (Bovine Serum Albumin) in PBS for 10 min. Blocking was performed in a blocking solution (2% BSA in PBS) for 30 min. Primary antibodies were incubated in the blocking solution for 1 hr. The following antibodies were used- anti- α -tubulin mouse IgG monoclonal (T5168, Sigma-Aldrich; 1:100); anti-laminin B1 rabbit IgG polyclonal (ab16048, Abcam; 1:200); anti-centromere protein human IgG polyclonal (15-234, Antibodies Incorporated; 1:400). Subsequently, after washing in PBS, cells were incubated for 40 min with the following secondary antibodies in blocking solution- Alexa Fluor 488 donkey anti-mouse IgG (A-21202, Thermo Fisher Scientific; 1:400); Cy3 donkey anti-rabbit IgG (711-165-152, Jackson ImmunoResearch; 1:400); Cy5 goat anti-human IgG (109-175-088, Jackson ImmunoResearch; 1:50). Finally, cells were also counterstained with DAPI (4',6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole dihydrochloride, D9542, Sigma-Aldrich; 1:40000) for 15 min before the mounting step. All the steps were performed at room temperature. The samples were then mounted in Mowiol-DABCO and acquired with a spinning disk system as described below. At least 200 non-overlapping and randomly distributed fields of view were acquired and analyzed.

Acquisitions of HT-LIF24 dataset

All images were acquired using a spinning disk confocal system, consisting of a CrestOptics V3 Light scan-head (configured with 50 μ m-pinholes) mounted on a Nikon Ti2-E inverted microscope equipped with a motorized stage and a Photometrics Prime 95B 25 mm camera (pixel size 11 μ m). The samples were acquired with a Plan Apochromat Lambda S 40x/1.25 silicon immersion objective using Celesta Lumencor solid-state lasers as the light source. Fluorescence was collected using 19 different lightpath configurations. In each configuration, a penta-band excitation filter (MXR00543-CELESTA-DAPI/FITC/TRITC/Cy5/Cy7-Full Multiband Penta), a penta-band dichroic filter (MXR00543-CELESTA-DAPI/FITC/TRITC/Cy5/Cy7-Full Multiband Penta) and a penta-band emission filter (Semrock FF01-441/511/593/684/817-25) were used. Ground truth images were acquired using a specific additional band-pass emission filter inserted before the penta-band emission filter (in particular the DAPI, FITC, TRITC, and Cy5 emission filters were added for GT-A, GT-B, GT-C, and GT-D configurations, respectively), while for all the other channels only the penta-band emission filter was used. The excitation wavelengths of the 19 channels were set as follows - GT-A - 405 nm (40%); GT-B - 477 nm (35%); GT-C - 547 nm (5%); GT-D - 638 nm (50%); A - 405 nm (40%); B - 477 nm (35%); C - 547 nm (5%); D - 638 nm (50%); AB - 405 nm (40%), 477 nm (35%); AC - 405 nm (40%), 547 nm (5%); AD - 405 nm (40%), 638 nm (50%); BC - 477 nm (35%), 547 nm (5%); BD - 477 nm (35%), 638 nm (50%); CD - 547 nm (5%), 638 nm (50%); ABC - 405 nm (40%), 477 nm (35%), 547 nm (5%); ABD - 405 nm (40%), 477 nm (35%), 638 nm (50%); ACD - 405 nm (40%), 547 nm (5%), 638 nm (50%); BCD - 477 nm (35%), 547 nm (5%), 638 nm (50%); ABCD - 405 nm (40%), 477 nm (35%), 547 nm (5%), 638 nm (50%). All images were acquired at binning 1. For each field of view, a series of images was captured using the following exposure times - 2 ms, 3 ms, 5 ms, 20 ms, 500 ms. The software used for all acquisitions was NIS Element AR 5.42.02 (Nikon).

Simply put, it has 4 different structures- (i) A - the whole nuclei (DAPI staining), (ii) B - microtubules: one component of the cytoskeleton, which is a filamentous system in the cytoplasm (alpha-tubulin staining), (iii) C - nuclear envelope- the membrane that separates the nucleus from the cytoplasm (Lamin B1 staining), (iv) D - the kinetochore/centromere- specific area along the chromosomes-DNA which is used to connect the chromosomes themselves to the microtubules during mitosis (CREST staining).

F.6 The Chicago-Sch23 dataset

This dataset is four-color structured illumination super-resolution microscopy imaging of live human BJ fibroblast cells acquired at the Scherer Lab at the University of Chicago, Chicago, USA [24]. It has 4 channels of different structures: (1) actins (CellMask Orange), (2) mitochondria (MitoTracker Green), (3) microtubules (Tubulin Tracker Deep Red), and (4) nuclei (Hoechst).

Sample preparation

Human BJ fibroblast cells were cultured in high-glucose DMEM (Life Technologies, 10569) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (Life Technologies, 26140) and penicillin-streptomycin. Cells were maintained in a humidified incubator at 37 degrees Celsius with 5% carbon dioxide. Prior to imaging, live cells were washed with PBS (Life Technologies, 15140) and trypsinized using 2.5 mL of 0.05% trypsin (Life Technologies, 25300) at 70–80% confluence. The cells were then transferred to 35 mm glass-bottom dishes (MatTek, P35G-1.5-14-C) for microscopy.

The staining solution was prepared by diluting Tubulin Tracker Deep Red (Thermo Fisher Scientific, T34077) to $1x$, CellMask Orange Actin Tracking Stain (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A57247) to $2x$, MitoTracker Green FM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, M7514) to 100 nM, and Hoechst 34580 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, H21486) to $5\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in growth media. For imaging, cells were incubated with 1mL of the staining solution for 30 minutes at 37 degree Celsius, rinsed five times with FluoroBrite DMEM (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A1896701), and subsequently imaged and analyzed in FluoroBrite DMEM.

Multi-color structured illumination microscopy (SIM) super-resolution imaging

A custom-built structured illumination microscope (SIM) was used for multi-color imaging¹. Excitation wavelengths of 642nm (Spectra-Physics, Excelsior One 642), 532nm (Spectra-Physics, Millennia V), 488nm (Spectra-Physics, Excelsior One 488), and 405nm (Spectra-Physics, Excelsior One 405) were employed to excite Tubulin Tracker, CellMask Orange, MitoTracker, and Hoechst, respectively. The four laser beams were combined using three dichroic mirrors (Semrock, Di03-R405-t1; Semrock, Di03-R488-t1; Thorlabs, DMSP550R) and subsequently expanded by 4x. The combined beams were first diffracted into monochromatic beams by a blazed grating (Thorlabs, GR13-0605) and then recombined at the plane of a digital micromirror device (DMD; Texas Instruments, DLP9000X VIS WQXGA). The DMD-generated patterns were projected onto the sample plane through an objective lens (Nikon, SR Plan Apo, 60x, 1.27 WI). A multi-band dichroic mirror (Semrock, Di01-R405/488/532/635-25x36) and an emission filter (Semrock, FF01-446/510/581/703-25) were used to separate excitation and emission light. Additionally, a $2\times$ beam expander was employed to further magnify the emission signal, resulting in a total magnification of $120\times$. Fluorescence images were captured using an sCMOS detector (Photometrics, Kinetix).

For SIM super-resolution imaging, striped binary patterns with a second-order spatial frequency of $2.86\mu\text{m}^{-1}$ at the sample plane were displayed on the DMD. Patterns at three different angles with six phase shifts each were sequentially projected, with an exposure time of 100 ms per pattern. Super-resolution SIM reconstruction was performed using FairSIM 2, an ImageJ-based open-source software. Each raw image stack of $2048 \times 2048 \times 18$ was reconstructed into 4096×4096 super-resolution images, where each pixel corresponds to 27 nm.

F.7 The HHMI-D25 dataset

Animal Experiments:

Heterozygous PhAMexcised female mice carrying the Mito-Dendra2 transgene were generated through in-house breeding: first, PhAMexcised heterozygous males and females (strain #018397, Jackson Laboratories) were crossed to derive homozygous males, which were then bred with wild-type C57BL/6J females. Mice were housed in sound-attenuated, temperature- and humidity-controlled rooms under a 12-hour light/dark cycle, with food and water provided ad libitum. All procedures were conducted in accordance with NIH guidelines and were approved by the Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) at the Janelia Research Campus (Protocol #22-0229.04). Livers were collected via cardiac perfusion: first with $1\times$ PBS to remove blood, followed by 30 mL of 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) at a flow rate of 2.5 mL/min to minimize endothelial damage. Tissues were post-fixed in 4% PFA for 24 hours, rinsed three times in $1\times$ PBS, and stored in 1% PFA until further processing.

Immunostaining and Image Acquisition:

For imaging, samples were embedded in 4.6% low-melting-point agarose and sectioned into 120 μm slices using a Leica VT 1200S vibratome. Sections were blocked in 10% fetal bovine serum with 0.5% Triton X-100 for 1 hour and incubated with primary antibodies at 4°C for 48 hours. Mouse anti-PMP70 (MilliporeSigma, SAB4200181, 1:75) and rabbit anti-LAMP1 (Abcam, AB208943, 1:50) were used to label peroxisomes and lysosomes, respectively. Secondary antibodies — Alexa Fluor 647 goat anti-mouse (Thermo Fisher, A21235, 1:500) and Alexa Fluor 750 goat anti-rabbit (Thermo Fisher, A21039, 1:500) — were applied overnight at

4°C. Additional markers included Alexa Fluor Plus 555 Phalloidin (Thermo Fisher, A30106, 1:100) and HCS LipidTox Red (Thermo Fisher, H34476, 1:100) to label actin and lipid droplets, respectively. Nuclei were stained with DAPI (Thermo Fisher, D3571, 1:1000 dilution of 1 mg/mL stock) during a 25-minute PBS wash the following day. Sections were cleared using EasyIndex (LifeCanvas Technologies, EI-500-1.52) by incubating samples first in 50% EasyIndex for 1 hour, followed by 100% EasyIndex for 3–5 hours, and mounted using Secure-Seal spacers (Thermo Fisher, 0523073). Imaging was performed on a Leica Stellaris 8 confocal microscope using a 63×/1.40 NA oil immersion objective. Images were acquired at 2048 × 2048 pixels using bidirectional scanning, 2× optical zoom, and a pinhole size of 0.5 Airy units (AU). A total depth of 10μm was captured across 50 z-sections. Fluorophores were imaged using two acquisition lines: the first included mitochondria, actin, and lysosomes, while the second included nuclei, lipid droplets, and peroxisomes.

G Further Details on all Experiments (Learning Tasks)

In this section, we mention specific details about individual tasks mentioned in the Table 1. Unless explicitly specified, we use the same hyperparameters for all tasks. Please refer to the code for details on the hyperparameters.

G.1 Two-channel semantic unmixing tasks

Task I

It is created from the HT-H24 dataset. It works on 3D z-stacks. The acquisition mode used in this dataset was *Training Mode I*. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S18.

Task II

It is created from HT-P23A dataset. It works on 3D z-stacks. The acquisition mode used in this dataset was *Training Mode I*. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S19.

Task III

It is created from the HT-P23B dataset. It works on 3D z-stacks. The acquisition mode used in this dataset was *Training Mode I*. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S20.

Task IV-XII

These tasks are created from the Pavia-P24 dataset. The acquisition mode used in them was *Training Mode III-a*. These tasks work on 2D frames. There are nine different acquisitions within this dataset that differ in (a) the laser power distribution among the two target channels and (b) the overall SNR. SNR has three levels, namely low, mid, and high, with low having the lowest SNR and high having the highest SNR level. The SNR level fixes the total combined laser power used for both channels. Within a single SNR level, we distribute the power among the two channels in three ways, namely, 50/50, 66/33, and 84/16 denoting the percentage laser power allocation to the respective channel. So, 84/16 means 84% of the total laser power was allocated to channel 1 and 16% was allocated to channel 2. We show one qualitative example per task in Supplementary Figures S27, S29, S28, S30, S31, S32, S33, S34, S35.

Task XIII

This task was created from the HT-T24 dataset. It works on 2D frames. The acquisition mode used in them was *Training Mode III-a*. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S36.

Task XIV

This task was created from the HT-LIF dataset. It used (Nucleus) and Microtubules as the two channels. It works on 2D frames. The acquisition mode used in them was *Training Mode III-a*. This task worked with the sub-dataset that had the exposure duration of 5ms. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S37.

Task XV-XX

These tasks were created from the Chicago-Sch23 dataset. The Chicago-Sch23 dataset has four structures, and these tasks capture all possible 2-channel semantic unmixing tasks from these four structures. These are Structured Illumination Microscopy (SIM) images, and due to the computational post-processing that happens in SIM, the resulting images have very different noise characteristics. Therefore, we disabled the use of noise models for all tasks generated from the Chicago-Sch23 dataset. More specifically, in Equation 2, we set $w = 0$. We show one qualitative example per task in Supplementary Figures S21, S22, S23, S24, S25, S26.

G.2 Three-channel semantic unmixing tasks

Task XXI

This task is a 3-channel semantic unmixing task generated from the CBG-Z18 dataset. This is a 3D dataset and so, we employ the 3D version of MicroSplit. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S16.

Task XXII

This task is a 3-channel semantic unmixing task generated from the CBG-N18 dataset. This is a 3D dataset and so, we employ the 3D version of MicroSplit. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S17.

Task XXIII

This task is a 3-channel 3D semantic unmixing task generated from HHMI-D25 dataset. Specifically, mitochondria, lysosomes and nuclei channels from HHMI-D25_{8bit} sub-dataset is used to create this task. This is a 3D dataset and so, we employ 3D version of MicroSplit. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S57.

Tasks XXIV-XXVIII

These tasks are generated from the HT-LIF24 dataset which has four structures. The three structures picked for these tasks are Nucleus, Microtubules and Kinetocore. While these tasks aim at splitting apart the above-mentioned three structures, they differ in the exposure duration of the training and evaluation dataset. The exposure duration used is mentioned in *Task Details* column of Table 1.

We show one qualitative example per task in Supplementary Figures S13, S14, S15, S11, S12.

Task XXXI, XXXII

These two tasks are 3-channel 3D semantic unmixing tasks generated from the denoised version of HHMI-D25_{8bit} dataset, with denoising done by Noise2Void [4]. Mitochondria, lysosomes and nuclei channels from HHMI-D25_{8bit} sub-dataset are used. This is a 3D dataset and so, we employ 3D version of MicroSplit. While the task XXXI works directly on the above-mentioned data whereas task XXXII adds Gaussian and Poisson noise on top of the individual channels. Please refer to Supplementary sub-section B.1.1 on how the noise was added. On a technical note, since the task XXXI directly works on the denoised data, there is no rationale to use noise models on such data. Hence the denoSplit loss component is completely disabled ($w = 0$ in Equation 1) and the Task XXXI is effectively trained with μ Split configuration. We show one qualitative example for each task in Supplementary Figure S61.

Task XXXIII-XXXV

These three tasks are 3-channel 3D semantic unmixing tasks generated from HHMI-D25_{16bit} dataset. Mitochondria, lysosomes and nuclei channels from HHMI-D25_{16bit} sub-dataset are used. This is a 3D dataset and so, we employ 3D version of MicroSplit. While the task XXXIII works directly on the above-mentioned data whereas tasks XXXIV and XXXV adds Gaussian and Poisson noise on top of the individual channels. Please refer to Supplementary sub-section B.1.1 on how the noise was added. We show one qualitative example for each task in Supplementary Figure S62.

Task XXXVI

This task is a 3-channel 3D semantic unmixing task generated from HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25} dataset. Mitochondria, lysosomes and nuclei channels from HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25} sub-dataset are used. This is a 3D dataset and

Training Mode	Correlation between structures preserved?	Input data is...	Note
<i>Training Mode I</i>	Yes	... mixed computationally.	Existing imaging data can be used (no special acquisitions required).
<i>Training Mode II</i>	No	... mixed computationally.	Existing imaging data can be used (no special acquisitions required). Results might be of lesser quality if reliable structural correlations between channels to be unmixed do exist.
<i>Training Mode III</i>	Yes	... imaged directly.	Mixed input must directly be imaged along with the individual target channels. Can lead to best performance when imaging is done well, but requires additional microscopy work.

Table ST11 Overview of Training Modes: Properties and key advantages/ disadvantages of the training modes we propose. We say that the correlation between structures is preserved when their relative positioning in the computationally mixed input maintains their biologically occurring relative positioning in the sample.

so, we employ 3D version of MicroSplit. We show one qualitative example for the task in Supplementary Figure S59.

G.3 Four-channel semantic unmixing tasks

Task XXIX

This task is generated from the HT-LIF24 dataset and uses all four structures to create this task. The exposure duration used for this task is 5ms. We show one qualitative example per task in Figure 1f.

Task XXX

This task is generated from the Chicago-Sch23 dataset and uses all four structures to create this task. Due to the same reason as described for Tasks XV–XX, we have disabled the Noise model for this task as well. We show one qualitative example in Supplementary Figure S10.

Task Idx	Dataset	Task Details	2D/3D	PSNR		MicroMS-SSIM	
				C1	C2	C1	C2
I	HT-H24	-	3D	0.09	0.55	0.973	0.956
II	HT-P23A	-	3D	0.53	0.45	0.016	0.006
III	HT-P23B	-	3D	0.29	0.39	0.005	0.019
IV	Pavia-P24	high, 50/50	2D	0.17	1.1	0.010	0.009
V	Pavia-P24	high, 66/33	2D	1.83	0.19	0.045	0.002
VI	Pavia-P24	high, 84/16	2D	0.35	1.44	0.016	0.049
VII	Pavia-P24	mid, 50/50	2D	0.26	0.55	0.005	0.013
VIII	Pavia-P24	mid, 66/33	2D	0.25	0.09	0.009	0.003
IX	Pavia-P24	mid,84/16	2D	0.02	0.42	0.005	0.006
X	Pavia-P24	low, 50/50	2D	0.41	0.42	0.010	0.012
XI	Pavia-P24	low, 66/33	2D	0.02	0.28	0.006	0.006
XII	Pavia-P24	low, 84/16	2D	0.72	0.76	0.025	0.018
XIII	HT-T24	-	2D	0.66	0.52	0.005	0.004
XIV	HT-LIF24	-	2D	0.66	1.21	0.003	0.004
XV	Chicago-Sch23	C0 vs C1	2D	1.80	0.92	0.003	0.001
XVI	Chicago-Sch23	C0 vs C2	2D	1.68	1.32	0.005	0.002
XVII	Chicago-Sch23	C0 vs C3	2D	1.20	0.54	0.000	0.000
XVIII	Chicago-Sch23	C1 vs C2	2D	0.89	1.46	0.001	0.001
XIX	Chicago-Sch23	C1 vs C3	2D	0.99	0.81	0.000	0.001
XX	Chicago-Sch23	C2 vs C3	2D	1.01	0.82	0.000	0.000

Task Idx	Dataset	Task Details	2D/3D	PSNR			MicroMS-SSIM		
				C1	C2	C3	C1	C2	C3
XXI	CBG-Z18	-	3D	0.12	0.18	0.12	0.002	0.001	0.001
XXII	CBG-N18	-	3D	0.18	0.21	0.06	0.000	0.000	0.000
XXIII	HHMI-D25 _{8bit}	-	3D	0.018	0.035	0.027	0.000	0.002	0.001
XXIV	HT-LIF24	2ms	2D	1.19	0.90	0.66	0.007	0.003	0.004
XXV	HT-LIF24	3ms	2D	1.30	0.96	0.75	0.008	0.003	0.004
XXVI	HT-LIF24	5ms	2D	1.11	0.89	0.53	0.004	0.002	0.004
XXVII	HT-LIF24	20ms	2D	0.85	0.62	0.73	0.002	0.001	0.002
XXVIII	HT-LIF24	500ms	2D	0.61	0.35	0.66	0.001	0.001	0.001
XXXI	HHMI-D25 _{8bit,denoised}	-	3D	0.073	0.11	0.151	0.000	0.001	0.001
XXXII	HHMI-D25 _{8bit,denoised}	$\sigma = 20, \lambda = 30$	3D	0.076	0.094	0.153	0.000	0.003	0.002
XXXIII	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	-	3D	0.03	0.126	0.016	0.002	0.003	0.001
XXXIV	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	$\sigma = 2K, \lambda = 5K$	3D	0.031	0.13	0.014	0.002	0.003	0.001
XXXV	HHMI-D25 _{16bit}	$\sigma = 4K, \lambda = 10K$	3D	0.033	0.133	0.016	0.002	0.004	0.001
XXXVI	HHMI-D25 _{16bit,0.25}	-	3D	0.082	0.103	0.021	0.000	0.001	0.000

Task Idx	Dataset	2D/3D	PSNR				MicroMS-SSIM			
			C1	C2	C3	C4	C1	C2	C3	C4
XXIX	HT-LIF24	2D	0.78	1.05	0.86	0.53	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.006
XXX	Chicago-Sch23	2D	1.57	0.87	1.24	0.65	0.006	0.002	0.003	0.008

Table ST12 Standard error values for all entries of Table 1.

A

Fig. S2 Semantic unmixing of similar structures with MicroSplit. We show how the same structure in two target channels can still be unmixed, even if the only structural difference is a controllable scaling factor. See Supplementary Section B.3 for a detailed description of the conducted experiments.

Fig. S3 Semantic unmixing of similar structures with MicroSplit. Here we plot *Validation PSNR vs. training steps* for all experiments shown in Figure S2. Observe that, as the magnification factor gets closer to 1, it takes longer for the network to initiate the learning, and the quality of the splitting converges to an overall lower level. See Supplementary Section B.3 for a detailed description of the conducted experiments.

Fig. S4 Comparison with PICASSO on a 3-channel unmixing task. Please note that MicroSplit distinguishes itself from PICASSO [20] by only requiring a single superimposed image as input, rather than multiple images with different spectral overlaps. Here, we used the high-SNR data from the HT-LIF24 dataset, prepared inputs that are suitable for PICASSO, and added additional (synthetic) noise to demonstrate how different both systems deal with noisy data. In row 1, we show example images from the the three input channels used for PICASSO. In rows 2 and 3, we show prediction by PICASSO and MicroSplit, respectively. In the last row, we show the high-SNR ground truth for visual evaluation. We observe that, in the presence of noise, Picasso starts to be challenged to unmix the data, mostly if it starts having similar features (see columns 2 and 3, where Picasso removes data around the nucleus region seen in column 1).

Fig. S5 Quantitative evaluations of the effect of signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) on in-distribution and out-of-distribution unmixing results (using the HT-LIF24 dataset). We trained MicroSplit models on micrographs acquired using a range of different exposure times. Note that the underlying sample ROIs remain identical. We then used all trained models (for 2ms, 3ms, 5ms, 20ms and 500ms exposure time data, indicated in the legend) and evaluated their semantic unmixing performance on all exposure times (x-axis), respectively. The rows show unmixed results quantified using MicroSSIM, MicroMS-SSIM, CARE-PSNR, SSIM and MS-SSIM metrics. All plots utilize the legend presented in the plot in the first row, first column. Note that the plots in this figure also demonstrate that the MS-SSIM and SSIM metrics do not work well on microscopy data (while MicroSSIM and MicroMS-SSIM show better sensitivity [8]).

Acq. Duration	GT Noisy vs GT High-SNR						Prediction vs GT High-SNR					
	PSNR			MicroMS-SSIM			PSNR			MicroMS-SSIM		
	C1	C2	C3	C1	C2	C3	C1	C2	C3	C1	C2	C3
2ms	23.3	25.1	26.1	0.839	0.772	0.869	31.0	32.2	36.3	0.940	0.973	0.944
3ms	23.6	26.0	27.2	0.842	0.780	0.871	30.8	32.2	36.1	0.940	0.973	0.948
5ms	24.6	28.3	29.9	0.857	0.817	0.875	32.9	34.3	37.6	0.960	0.983	0.963
20ms	30.0	35.6	38.16	0.920	0.942	0.914	37.0	39.7	41.4	0.984	0.994	0.989

Fig. S6 Photon efficient imaging with MicroSplit: a concrete example. We quantify two mechanisms through which MicroSplit reduces the required photon budget: (i) *Reduced photon filtering (top)*: Emission spectra of the three fluorophores DAPI, FITC, and TRITC are shown together with example emission filter bands used in conventional multi-color imaging. From left to right, we illustrate three settings that increasingly trade off bleed-through (BT) against photon efficiency: a configuration that strongly suppresses BT, a balanced configuration that collects more photons at the cost of some BT, and a highly permissive configuration that captures nearly all emitted photons but suffers notable spectral overlap. MicroSplit, by contrast, allows imaging multiple structures within a single broad emission band and subsequently reassigning the collected intensities to their respective output channels leading to the indicated photon-efficiency increases. (ii) *Denosing (bottom)*: Denoising enables repurposing of the available photon budget by acquiring lower-SNR micrographs, which MicroSplit can restore to high-SNR predictions. We compare raw data acquired at 2ms, 3ms, 5ms, and 20ms exposure times with high-SNR (500ms) reference images of the same regions in the HT-LIF24 dataset (three channels: Nucleus, Microtubules, Kinetochores). The first six data columns in the table quantify the similarity of low-exposure raw data to the 500ms reference, while the rightmost six columns show the corresponding similarities for MicroSplit predictions (identical data as in Table 1). In all cases, the MicroSplit predictions exhibit higher quality than the corresponding raw inputs. Strikingly, predictions from 2ms exposures already surpass the quality of 5ms raw data for all channels, and for Channel 1 even exceed the 20ms raw data. In this example, this corresponds to at least a three-fold reduction in required photon budget per acquisition, and likely closer to an order of magnitude when averaged across the three channels.

Fig. S7 Segmentation results using common combined labels. In Fig. 3, for training the segmentation model, analysts annotated the target images and trained the segmentation model on target images with those annotations. Similar steps were taken for prediction images. In this experiment, we combined the annotations of both target and prediction images and trained three models, one for target images, one for prediction images, and one for the input images. The purpose for training the segmentation model on the input images was to ascertain whether one can segment one structure from the superimposed input itself. The motivation to use common annotations for training all segmentation models using common annotations was to eliminate the situation where annotation for either target or prediction images were imperfect and hence the segmentation results became inferior to what they should otherwise be.

Fig. S8 Unmixing unequally intense channels. Here, we investigate what happens when one of the channels to be unmixed is much dimmer than the other (we called the divergence of structure intensities ‘skew’ in the main text). We used Tubulin and Nucleus channel from the 4 channel Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Line graphs of Tubulin and Nuclei shows that nucleus channel is considerably dimmer, such that the signal amplitude of this channel is only around the noise amplitude of the Tubulin channel. For every patch, we visualize half of the patch in *LogNorm* so that even the faintest signal becomes visible. We intend to answer the question whether the prediction of nucleus channel is mostly due to learned spatial correlation with the Tubulin channel or if the trained model is indeed capable to unmix such highly skewed intensities. To answer this question, we first trained the MicroSplit network on the original data and then conducted three test-time experiments (showing one per row in the figure). For these experiments, we picked a location in test data which contained both nucleus and tubulin. MicroSplit was training using *Training Mode I*. (a) We evaluate on the superimposed image patch created from the pre-selected location. (b) We tinkered with the inter-structure spatial correlations by shifting the nucleus channel relative to tubulin channel consistently by 1000 pixels. (c) We removed nuclei from the nucleus channel entirely by replacing them with background patches from the same channel. The results clearly indicate that MicroSplit was able to unmix the dim nucleus signals, even if the spatial correlation with the tubulin channel was tinkered with (observe the last two columns, *i.e.* ground truth *vs.* prediction of the nucleus channel).

Fig. S9 Task II, HT-P23A This task has a high skew with Mitochondria channel (Ch1) being weaker than Microtubule channel (Ch2), so much so that it is difficult to locate the Mitochondria in the superimposed input. MicroSplit MMSE predictions are subject to a certain ‘blurriness’ which indicates the model’s inability to give a consistent prediction for the Mitochondria channel.

Fig. S10 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXX from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S11 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXVII from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S12 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXVIII from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S13 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXIV from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S14 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXV from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S15 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXVI from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S16 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXI from CBG-Z18 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S17 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXII from CBG-N18 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S18 Qualitative Evaluation for Task I from HT-H24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S19 Qualitative Evaluation for Task II from HT-P23A dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S20 Qualitative Evaluation for Task III from HT-P23B dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S21 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XV from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S22 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XVI from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S23 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XVII from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S24 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XVIII from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S25 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XIX from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S26 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XX from Chicago-Sch23 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S27 Qualitative Evaluation for Task IV from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S28 Qualitative Evaluation for Task VI from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S29 Qualitative Evaluation for Task V from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S30 Qualitative Evaluation for Task VII from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S31 Qualitative Evaluation for Task VIII from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S32 Qualitative Evaluation for Task IX from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S33 Qualitative Evaluation for Task X from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S34 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XI from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S35 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XII from Pavia-P24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S36 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XIII from HT-T24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S37 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XIV from HT-LIF24 dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S38 Calibration plot for Task XIV from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S39 Calibration plot for Task XXVIII from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S40 Calibration plot for Task XXVI from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S41 Calibration plot for Task XXVII from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S42 Calibration plot for Task XXIII from Dataset HT-LIF24 2ms

Fig. S43 Calibration plot for Task XXIV from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S44 Calibration plot for Task XXV from Dataset HT-LIF24

Fig. S45 Calibration plot for Task V from Dataset Pavia-P24, mediumskew, high

Fig. S46 Calibration plot for Task VII from Dataset Pavia-P24, balanced, medium

Fig. S47 Calibration plot for Task VIII from Dataset Pavia-P24, mediumskew, medium

Fig. S48 Calibration plot for Task IX from Dataset Pavia-P24, highskew medium

Fig. S49 Calibration plot for Task X from Dataset Pavia-P24, balanced low

Fig. S50 Calibration plot for Task XI from Dataset Pavia-P24, mediumskew, low

Fig. S51 Calibration plot for Task XII from Dataset Pavia-P24, highskew, low

Fig. S52 Calibration plot for Task XX from Dataset Pavia-P24, balanced, high

Fig. S53 Calibration plot for Task IV from Dataset Pavia-P24, highskew, high

Fig. S54 Calibration plot for Task I from Dataset HT-H24

Fig. S55 Calibration plot for Task XXI from Dataset CBZ-Z18

Fig. S56 Calibration plot for Task XXII from Dataset CBZ-N18

Fig. S57 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXIII from HHMI-D25_{8bit} dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle. Also note that the predictions for channel 3 are of rather poor quality and that you can find a description of how this problem was solved in the Supplementary Section B.

Fig. S58 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXXIII from HHMI-D25_{16bit} dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S59 Qualitative Evaluation for Task XXXVI from HHMI-D25_{16bit,0.25} dataset. Note that we show the target and the prediction corresponding to the input crop which is denoted in *Input* panel by a white dotted rectangle.

Fig. S60 Effect of SNR on Model Performance (HT-LIF24 Dataset): We evaluate how SNR influences model performance using the HT-LIF24 dataset. Different models are trained on data subsets acquired with varying exposure durations—leading to different SNRs—and their predictions are compared over a common region of interest. High-frequency details in the predictions (especially the third channel) are visibly reduced when the input SNR is lower.

Fig. S61 Effect of SNR on Model Performance (HHMI-D25_{8bit} Dataset): We assess the impact of SNR on a subset of the HHMI-D25 dataset. Comparing the predictions (row 2, results of Task XXIII) with the ground truth (row 1), we observe that the prediction quality, particularly for the third channel, is not good, with entire parts of the structures being put into the other channels. We then train MicroSplit using a Noise2Void [4] denoised version of the same data, leading to much improved semantic unmixing performance (row 3, Task XXXI). Finally, we re-introduced synthetic Gaussian and Poisson noise to the denoised HHMI-D25 data used in Task XXXI and retrained MicroSplit on this lower-SNR data (row 4, Task XXXII). As it was likely to be expected, this does again drop the semantic unmixing performance.

Fig. S62 Effect of SNR on Model Performance (HHMI-D25_{16bit} Dataset): We assess the impact of SNR on the HHMI-D25_{16bit} dataset. For this part of the HHMI-D25 data, the predictions (row 2, Task XXXIII) are visually more close to the target images compared to results on HHMI-D25_{8bit} dataset (Figure S61, row 2, Task XXIII). We then introduce two levels of additional Gaussian and Poisson noise to the HHMI-D25_{16bit} data to reduce SNR and retrain MicroSplit on those noisier versions of the data (row 3 and 4, Tasks XXXIV and XXXV, respectively). As it was likely to be expected, the reduced SNR leads to a noticeable decline in the semantic unmixing performance.